

**CONNECTING LANDSCAPE
ARCHITECTURE ARCHIVES**

**TO ENHANCE EUROPEAN LANDSCAPE
PRACTICE, RESEARCH AND EDUCATION**

CATALOGUE

Teaching with landscape architecture archives

Edited by Marlies Brinkhuijsen, Lei Gao and Güzin Yeliz Kahya

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Figure 1: Students studying maps of Crawley, a newtown from the late 1940s, in the West Sussex Archive in Chichester. Photo Wim Bosschaart, 2026.

Introduction

Catalogue: examples of teaching with landscape architecture archives

Lei Gao, Güzin Yeliz Kahya, Marlies Brinkhuijsen

This Catalogue is the result of a collaborative effort and represents one of the primary outputs of the EU funded COST Action: *Connecting landscape architecture archives to enhance landscape practice, research and education* (ConnectLAA, 2024-2028). The Catalogue compiles 30 peer-reviewed examples of courses and teaching modules that integrate archives and archival materials as pedagogical sources. These examples serve as a source of inspiration for educators, students, and researchers in landscape architecture and related disciplines such as architecture, spatial planning, and architectural history. A detailed navigation map is provided at the end of this introduction to help the readers identify relevant examples for their needs.

About COST Action - ConnectLAA

ConnectLAA started in October 2024 and lasts for four years. Through a series of interdisciplinary, intersectoral and international collaboration activities, ConnectLAA aims to create a multi-stakeholder Community of practice dedicated to the establishment of a comprehensive, sustainable European knowledge and exchange platform for LA archival records. It aims to bridge the gap between archival research and the practice of LA by incorporating a historical perspective, to enhance LA education and research, landscape history, historical continuity, and historically profound practice.

Through networking and exchange activities along and beyond the COST Action, a wide range of information will be made accessible for research (academic capacity building), for innovative practice (professional capacity building), archival practice (technological development) and education (innovative teaching methods). By supporting the process of founding, developing, improving, and enlarging LA archival collections and intensifying exchange between the actors involved, dispersed knowledge can be pooled and made accessible in analogue form and online on a data platform. Furthermore, in academic education the limited attention to LA history and proper documentation of the profession will be mitigated by innovative teaching approaches based on archives.

Improved online and analogue accessibility guarantees outreach to a wider public and lowers the threshold for spreading and increasing general knowledge. The public benefit from this by gaining accessibility to information about their living environment, providing general insights and facilitating civic engagement (interested landowners, tenants, and citizens). The Action addresses scholars, teachers, archivists, archival institutions, IT specialists, decision-making bodies, professionals, students, and the general public.¹

ConnectLAA has four Working groups (WG):

- WG1. Transfer archival knowledge to support LA archive management and operation
- WG2. Enhance the use of LA archives for research and practice
- WG3. Enhance education through the use of archives
- WG4. Communication and dissemination

While WG1 provides foundation and support for WG2 and WG3, WG2 and WG3 are the applications. WG4 promotes communication among WGs and broader stakeholders, as well as dissemination of results. Together they help connecting, strengthening and growing landscape architecture archives across Europe, and using them to enhance landscape practice, research and education, and ultimately benefit societies in Europe.

¹ COST Action 23128, MoU. https://e-services.cost.eu/files/domain_files/CA/Action_CA23128/mou/CA23128-e.pdf

Connecting landscape architecture archives with education

The overarching goal of the Working Group Education is to enhance education through the use of archives. Although the main focus is landscape architecture education at Bachelor, Master and PhD level in universities of Europe, it remains open for higher education in other related fields (such as architecture, planning, art history) and other types of education (such as continuous education for professionals and primary and secondary education). In terms of archives, the initial target is landscape architecture archives, but in reality many archival collections are stored in architectural or other archives, libraries and museums, or under private collections. Therefore all kinds of archives, archival collections and materials that relate to landscape architecture are within the working group's scope of exploration.

To reach the goal, the Working Group Education the working plan for the 4-year period includes:

- Year 1 (Oct. 2024-Oct. 2025): Map current tools and methods for the use of archives in higher education,
- Years 2-3 (Nov. 2025-Oct. 2027): Identify students' and teachers' needs and wishes, and co-develop innovative ways of teaching with archival materials,
- Year 4 (Nov. 2027-Oct. 2028): Set up a teachers' training and an online course for students on the use of archival materials.

This catalogue is the final product of Year 1, exhibiting examples of involving archives and archival materials in teaching. A step-by-step approach led to this final output. A survey to educational institutions and practice in Europe in early 2025 provided an initial understanding of how much archives have been used in what kind of courses. Among 249 responses, 89 have used archival materials in teaching. In May-June 2025 six regional workshops took place in different parts of Europe (see figure 2). The aim was to understand current pedagogical approaches and tools for integrating archival materials across a range of educational contexts in different regions. Concrete examples were presented to demonstrate best practices of using archives and archival materials in education. Invited guests, ConnectLAA members and their colleagues and students exchanged experiences of teaching and learning with archives and archival materials. Archivists were also invited in some of the workshops to show the rich collections and their potentials for education and professional practice. In June, the participants of all 6 regional workshops gathered online in a Joint Seminar to share their findings and try some hands-on methods of teaching with archival materials.

In autumn 2025, a call was launched to submit examples of teaching with landscape architecture archives for a publication aimed at showcasing effective uses of archives and archival materials in education. The call extended beyond presenters and participants of the regional workshops and invited all educators interested. 33 examples were received and went through a peer review and revision process. Eventually 30 examples are presented in this Catalogue.

How to use the Catalogue

This Catalogue is designed for educators in landscape architecture and related fields at universities, schools, museums and more, who are looking for inspiration, technical advice, or step-by-step guidance on involving archival materials in their teaching activities. To help educators identify the examples for their needs, the examples are organized according to study cycles (start from 1st year Bachelor). Of the 30 examples, 13 are designed for the Bachelor level and 15 for the Master level. Some additional examples cover doctoral education, teacher training and school education. Table 3 gives an overview of the examples and their teaching methods (*Group Work or Workshop, Tutorial, Lecture, Selfstudy, Design Studio, Fieldwork or Excursion*). Table 4 shows the didactic purposes (*Awareness Building, Knowledge Building, Inform Design or Action, Critical Reflection*) and didactic prompts for archival engagement. Definitions of the categories are provided in tables 5 and 6.

Table 3 indicates that the use of archival materials differs across curricular years. While integrating archival materials in lectures, tutorials and fieldwork are more frequently found in Bachelor-level courses and the first year of the Master, using archival materials in design studio teaching appears across almost all curricular years in both Bachelor and Master programmes. In terms of the pedagogical purposes, building awareness of archival use, using archival materials for knowledge building, and for design or action are present across all study cycles, but using archival materials to develop critical thinking (and critical reflection on archival materials) becomes more prominent towards the later phases of study programs. This distribution can serve as a reference for when and where to best integrate archival use within higher education curricula. While you may choose examples that align specifically with your current teaching types and levels, we recommend exploring entries beyond your primary target group, as valuable inspiration can also be found in unexpected places.

Regional workshops 2025

Portugal/Spain: 7 & 29 May 2025

Local organisers: Maria João Fonseca, Laura Jeschke & Ana Luisa Soares

The Netherlands: 14 May 2025

Local organiser: Marlies Brinkhuijsen

Turkey: 23 May 2025

Local organiser: Duygu Kalkan Açıkkapı

Latvia: 29 May 2025

Local organiser: Kristine Vugule

Norway: 12 June 2025

Local organisers: Lei Gao & Annegreth Dietze-Schirdewahn

United Kingdom: 17 June 2025

Local organisers: Guy Baxter & Luca Csepely-Knorr

Joint online seminar: 30 June 2025

Figure 2: In 2025, six regional workshops on teaching with landscape architecture archives took place across Europe. A review of the results took place during a joint online seminar.

List of examples

Descriptive Characteristics of the Examples						Teaching Methods					
Catalogue nr.	Phase	Year	Program	Country	Author	Group Work/ Workshop	Tutorial	Lecture	Selfstudy	Design Studio	Fieldwork/ Excursion
1	Ba	1	Landscape Architecture	Norway	Annegreth Dietze-Schirdewahn		x				
2	Ba	1	Landscape Engineering & Garden Engineering	Sweden	Anna Jakobsson	x	x				x
3	Ba	1 & 2	Landscape Architecture, Landscape Engineering & Garden Engineering	Sweden	Anna Jakobsson	x	x				
4	Ba	2	Urban Design and Landscape Architecture	Türkiye	Duygu Kalkan-Açikkapı		x	x	x		x
5	Ba	2	Art, Architecture, Media and Design	Netherlands	Imke van Hellemond		x	x			
6	Ba	2	Landscape Architecture	Netherlands	Lisanne Struckman		x			x	
7	Ba	2	Landscape Architecture	Türkiye	Abdullah Çigdem		x	x			
8	Ba	3	Architectural History	Netherlands	Imke van Hellemond		x	x	x		x
9	Ba	3	Landscape Architecture	France	Bernadette Blanchon		x				x
10	Ba	3	Landscape Architecture and Planning	Netherlands	Wim Bosschaart						x
11	Ba	4	Architecture	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Igor Kuvač					x	
12	Minor/Pre-master		Urbanism & Landscape Architecture	Netherlands	Imke van Hellemond			x			x
13	Ba/Ma		Landscape Architecture & Related Fields	Portugal	Laura Jeschke & Maria João Fonseca	x					
14	Ma	1	Architecture	Italy	Giulia Annalinda Neglia	x				x	x
15	Ma	1	Architectural History	Netherlands	Imke van Hellemond		x	x	x		x
16	Ma	1	Architectural History	Netherlands	Imke van Hellemond		x		x		
17	Ma	1	Landscape Architecture	Portugal	Paula Gomes da Silva		x				
18	Ma	1	Landscape Architecture & Architecture	Norway	Miguel Hernández Quintanilla	x	x		x		
19	Ma	1	Architecture & Urbanism	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Nevena Novaković & Dijana Simonović	x	x		x		
20	Ma	1	Architecture & Urbanism	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Igor Kuvač					x	
21	Ma	1	Architecture & Urbanism	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Dijana Simonović & Igor Kuvač					x	
22	Ma	1	Landscape Architecture	Norway	Jorg Sieweke					x	
23	Ma	2	Landscape Architecture	France	Agnès Prévost	x					
24	Ma	2	Landscape Architecture	Slovenia	Attila Tóth					x	
25	Ma	2	Landscape Architecture	France	Sonia Keravel & Bernadette Blanchon		x		x		
26	Ma	2	Landscape Design	Poland	Kinga Kirmic					x	
27	Ma	2	Architecture	United Kingdom	Joy Burgess & Luca Csepely-Knorr	x				x	
28	PhD	1	Heritage Studies	Portugal	Miguel Reimão Costa & Desidério Batista		x		x		
29	Teachers		Landscape Architecture & Related Fields	Spain	Maria João Fonseca & Laura Jeschke	x					
30	Primary school			United Kingdom	Joy Burgess, Luca Csepely-Knorr & Joan Anderson	x					

Table 3: List of examples and their types of teaching

Examples		Didactic Purposes				Didactic Prompts for Archival Engagement			
Catalogue nr.	Author	Awareness	Knowledge Building	Inform design or action	Critical Reflection	Relevancy	Type of Archival Materials	How and Where to Find	How to Analyse and Interpret
1	Annegreth Dietze-Schirdewahn	x	x	x					
2	Anna Jakobsson	x	x						x
3	Anna Jakobsson		x				x	x	x
4	Duygu Kalkan-Açikkapı	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
5	Imke van Hellemond	x	x						x
6	Lisane Struckman	x	x	x					
7	Abdullah Çigdem		x		x		x		x
8	Imke van Hellemond	x	x			x		x	x
9	Bernadette Blanchon	x	x			x		x	x
10	Wim Bosschaart	x	x		x				x
11	Igor Kuvač	x	x	x					x
12	Imke van Hellemond	x	x	x			x		x
13	Laura Jeschke & Maria João Fonseca		x	x	x		x		x
14	Giulia Annalinda Neglia	x	x	x		x	x		x
15	Imke van Hellemond	x	x		x	x		x	x
16	Imke van Hellemond	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
17	Paula Gomes da Silva		x		x				x
18	Miguel Hernández Quintanilla	x			x	x			x
19	Nevena Novaković & Dijana Simonović		x		x			x	x
20	Igor Kuvač		x	x					x
21	Dijana Simonović & Igor Kuvač	x	x	x				x	x
22	Jorg Sieweke		x	x					x
23	Agnès Prévost	x	x					x	-
24	Attila Tóth		x	x	x		x		x
25	Sonia Keravel & Bernadette Blanchon		x		x	x	x	x	x
26	Kinga Kimic		x	x			x	x	x
27	Joy Burgess & Luca Csepely-Knorr		x	x	x				x
28	Miguel Reimão Costa & Desidério Batista		x		x	x	x		x
29	Maria João Fonseca & Laura Jeschke	x		x			x		x
30	Joy Burgess, Luca Csepely-Knorr & Joan Anderson	x	x		x				x

Table 4: Didactic purposes of the examples

Teaching method	Description
Group work / Workshop	Students work together in a group on a project or topic introduced during a course. They (try to) solve problems that are complex enough to force students to divide tasks and roles to address the problem. The objective of group work can be diverse: broaden knowledge base, increase individual participation, learn collaboration/social skills. The lecturer is present for only a limited amount of time and can combine two roles: the expert (domain content and the final scientific product) and the process supervisor (coach, learning outcomes on collaboration skills and phases in group processes).
Tutorial	Students actively study and work with the subject matter, either individually or in a small group in an education room. Students apply and evaluate the knowledge and practice skills by making calculations, doing exercises etc. Teachers give plenary or in small groups feedback to students on their results and performance. This teaching method is suitable for almost all levels of cognitive learning outcomes.
Lecture	Offered in an education room by a teacher to facilitate a larger group of students to master scientific theories, discourses, concepts, methods, etc. With this teaching method, especially the lower cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy of learning can be achieved. Combined with interactive means and complex and challenging assignments, higher levels can be achieved.
Selfstudy	Students study the subject material independently. Lecturers only prepare and offer materials for study. Pure self-study is particularly suitable for learning outcomes with a low cognitive level (remember and understand knowledge). Feedback can be part of the self-study materials. Feedback sessions with the teacher are considered lectures or tutorials.
Design studio	Students actively and intensively learn about spatial challenges and practice design skills on a site. They practice individually or in pairs under close supervision. Students receive intensive, individual feedback on their performance and attendance is required during scheduled contact. This teaching method is suitable for all cognitive (remember, understand, apply, analyse, evaluate, create, etc.) and skill level learning outcomes (from imitation to naturalisation).
Fieldwork / Excursion	Students observe, experience, assess and evaluate real-life situations related to their study domain. They acquire knowledge through observation and analytical assignments of practical situations. Lecturers link 'practical experience' to theory and give feedback on the students' assignments. Learning is enhanced if students are required to carry out assignments before, during and after the excursion. This teaching method can be used for all cognitive and skill level learning outcomes.

Table 5: Description of teaching methods

Didactic purposes	Description
Awareness	Archives are introduced to create basic familiarity with their existence and with the historical context of the discipline. They function as a source of orientation recognizing that current practices are historically situated and shaped by earlier ideas, projects, and professional debates.
Knowledge Building	Archives are used as structured resources for developing disciplinary knowledge and supporting organized knowledge construction. Students engage critically with archival documents to extract information, compare cases, identify patterns, and understand methods and approaches within the discipline.
Inform Design or Action	Archives are used as active tools within the design process. They serve as a medium for translating historical insight into contemporary creative practice. Students actively integrate archival knowledge into the design decisions and action process, transforming historical understanding into practical outcomes.
Critical reflection	Archives are used to support critical and reflexive evaluation. They serve as a discursive and analytical tool for fostering the ability to challenge received knowledge, question power structures, and examine informed critiques.
Didactic Prompts for Archival Engagement	Description
Relevancy	Students are prompted to assess whether specific archives or documents are meaningful and appropriate for their research, project, or learning objectives.
Type of Archival Materials	Students are guided to identify, categorize, and understand the diversity of archival content, and to relate these materials to their research or learning objectives.
How and Where to find	Students are prompted to understand how archival materials are located, retrieved and accessed.
How to analyse and interpret	Students are prompted to engage critically and methodically with archival materials, understanding how to read, evaluate, and use it for scholarly or design purposes.

Table 6: Descriptions of didactic purposes and didactic prompts for archival engagement

Introduction to landscape architecture Drawing exercise

Landscape Architecture, 1st year Bachelor

Annegreth Dietze-Schirdewahn

Norwegian University of Life Sciences
Norway

Why teaching with archival materials?

This course introduces students to the scope and diversity of landscape architecture. It combines a range of thematic blocks, to give students an overview of the field of landscape architecture.

The intention of using archival material is to explore the history of landscape architecture through original drawings, plans, revealing diverse design approaches, styles, and representational techniques from earlier periods. In this case, the focus is not on a single project or a single point in time, but on a sequence of student projects from different decades. This allows shifts in style and approach to become visible, while the use of student work makes the material more relatable for current landscape architecture students, as these examples represent a group they can identify with.

Working with archival sources helps students understand how design thinking was conceived, communicated, and constructed in different historical contexts. Engaging with archival material provides inspiration for their own design work, while developing critical awareness of continuity and change within the discipline. Archival research also encourages reflection on how past landscape design works responded to social, cultural, and environmental conditions and how these insights can inform contemporary landscape architectural practice.

What will students learn?

- Identify and describe key historical approaches, design styles, and drawing techniques in landscape architecture using archival materials.
- Analyze archival drawings, plans, and texts to understand how design thinking was developed and represented in different periods.
- Reflect critically on historical landscape projects and their social, cultural, and environmental contexts.
- Apply insights gained from archival research to inform and inspire their own landscape architectural design work.

Learning activities and assessment

Students take lectures, do drawing exercises, read and join field visits. Teachers will discuss with students in smaller groups and provide oral feedback on smaller tasks. At the end of the course, students submit a portfolio containing their works on various tasks and receive a grade.

Key advice for teachers

Select 3–5 student projects from different decades and present them together, highlighting and comparing their design approaches and modes of expression. Discuss the differences among the examples and explore them through sketches.

As this is an introductory course, the teacher will collect and present the examples to the students. Due to capacity limits for larger groups, teachers prepare photographs of the archival documents and present them on the screen.

When presenting each project, start with the overall plan or map to give context, then gradually zoom in on specific details. Fascination often emerges when examining small sections of a drawing. Encourage students to observe and compare different styles and presentation methods, revealing the richness and depth of each project.

Assignment

1 Preparation

From the archive of old student works, the course teacher selects 3-5 student projects from different decades, and digitise the materials, so they can be viewed on the screen.

2 Presentation & discussion

The teacher presents the old student works to the class, highlighting and comparing their design approaches and modes of expression, in their contemporary contexts. Students and the teacher discuss the differences among the examples, analyse design styles, drawing techniques, and representational methods found in these archival sources, and identify the changes in design approaches and styles.

3 Sketching and interpretation

As a method of exploration, students make sketches of the archival sources. They interpret historical landscapes in relation to their social, cultural, and environmental contexts.

4 Translation

Students reflect on archival findings and translate historical insights into ideas or references for their own design work.

Figure 7: A few student projects selected from the Historical Archive of Norwegian Landscape Architecture. These works range from 1917 to 1959, exhibiting the changing scope of the projects and drawing styles over time. (Source of images: collections at the Historical Archive of Norwegian Landscape Architecture)

Garden history/Trädgårdshistoria Image analysis

Landscape Engineering & Garden Engineering Design, 1st year Bachelors

Anna Jakobsson

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)
Sweden

Why teaching with archival materials?

This is an assignment in a theory/history course. The assignment is to rephotograph an old photo (could be a postcard) and analyse differences and similarities in the photographs via overlays and transfers. The re-photography exercise is one of two analyses where students use archive material in this course (the other is an analysis of maps and plans, described in another entry). The results from this exercise are used to describe a site historically over time and to write about it in a shorter essay.

This exercise is a very useful assignment for landscape architect students in the first year as well and has occurred irregularly in that programme. It is also useful in thesis work, visualising change.

The analysis of archival sources is a part of a larger assignment to write a short essay on the history of for example a square, a park, residential areas or a street. The overall intention of this is to learn about landscape change, analysing different sources, but also to teach them where to find these sources of landscape history and use different techniques when analysing the material.

What will students learn?

- Interpret the history of a site, using a combination of field studies, historic photographs, text sources, plans, maps and other archive material.
- Describe spatial change over time and learn about design ideals and the use of plants and other materials in different time periods.

Learning activities and assessment

The students discuss the historic image as well as the site itself and the rephotograph in groups, which widens their interpretation and gives the opportunity for aha-moments. The analysis of the historic photo and the rephotograph is partly done in the studio, where they also learn from each other and from teachers' supervision. In the clarification of their analysis, with either transfers of structures or text explanations, they learn how to visualise spatial change over time. The students' hand-in consists of text descriptions of the rephotograph and of the old photo, the photos themselves and at least one image showing overlays and one image of a transfer of structures.

The hand-in is assessed when it comes to content and clarity. All parts should be there, and both the texts and the analyses must be clear and easy to interpret (with a legend explaining the colours in the overlays and transfers for example).

Key advice for teachers

This exercise is very good to do in groups of three students, so they can discuss photo angles and differences between the old and the new image, where to look for other archive material and be more efficient in making several different overlays and transfers. But as a single exercise, to get to know a site without writing an essay about it, it can also work perfectly to do individually. If possible, it is beneficial to mix students from different education programmes in the groups.

I usually start with handing out an historic photo to the students and say that "this is the site you are going to write about" and then make them go there, bringing the old photo with them, to see what it looks like today and rephotograph it. This gives them a direct aha-experience about spatial change instead of doing the other way around, giving them a site to study and then making them look for an old photo and take a new one. They come back, excited and inspired to continue the search for other old photos or plans in archives.

The old photograph does not have to be very old. The important thing is that the site has changed, a little or a lot. To encourage the students to continue their search for more archive material, the best thing is if the old photo (or postcard) is retrieved from an archive, either searchable online or otherwise accessible.

When doing transfers, the print/copy of the photo onto which the transfers are made is good to print a bit lighter than usual, so that the transfer drawn onto it will be more visible. To use colour pencils when doing transfers is recommendable, not necessarily green for vegetation and blue for water. Let the students experiment a bit. Brown and black together is usually not a good idea. Neither is light yellow or the combination of colours too close in brightness (light blue and turquoise for example).

In Sweden, old photos are free to use and alter when used in the education situation in the design studio. In unpublished written papers at the University, the students need to state the origins/source of the image and who has the copyright. If the material is going to be published (in a bachelor thesis for example) or shared outside the university (even to family and friends) the students also need the permission to share the image, apart from stating the origins/source and the copyright. These guidelines on the rights to use and publish the material can vary from country to country and from archive to archive (the creative commons licenses do not always apply), so this must be taken into consideration when planning this exercise.

Figure 8: The illustration shows a transfer of structures in an old photograph of the Botanical Garden in Lund onto a rephotograph, taken from the same angle in April 2025. The structures of the old photograph are drawn with colour pencils, and the newly taken photograph is printed in a light greyscale, for higher visibility. The changes of the paths, the water, the vegetation, and the changed use of the place are visualised. (Rephotography: Caroline Karlsson, student at SLU Alnarp, spring 2025. Transfer of structures from an old photo: Caroline Karlsson, spring 2025. The images are used with the student's permission)

Assignment

1 Describe photograph

Vegetation, material and spatial qualities of a site through an old photograph (very often from an old postcard).

2 Site visit

Rephotograph the site from the same angle as the old photo.

D3 describe differences

Describe the new photo the same way as the old one (vegetation, material, spatial qualities) and visually also describe the differences between the two photographs.

4 Analysis

Study the two photos more closely, constructing overlays on transparent sketching paper and by using a drawing board with lighting underneath.

5 Transfer structures

Clarify the analysis from the overlays by transferring either historic structures into the new photograph or an aerial photo from today, or transferring new structures into the old photograph.

6 Essay

The overlays and transfers made from the old and new photographs are used as illustrations in a short essay about the history of the site.

The total time for this is about 1 day (discussion, rephotograph/place visit, more discussion, analysis in studio, clarification).

References

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Meeting landscape & Garden history Map and aerial photo analysis

Landscape architecture, Landscape Engineering & Garden Engineering Design, 1st year Bachelors

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Why teaching with archival materials?

The task is to either analyse a part of a larger landscape historically (mainly done by landscape architects in the first year), or to analyse a specific site, a square or a housing area in a smaller scale (done by landscape engineers and garden engineers in the first year as well as landscape architects later in the programme). The intention of using archives is to teach the students to find historical information about a site, how to use/analyse it and how to describe/analyse landscape change in different scales. For the landscape engineer and garden engineer programmes, the analysis of maps and aerial photos is done as a part of a larger assignment to write an essay on the history of a specific site, so for them the intention is also to learn about the variation in different source materials.

What will students learn?

- Interpret and analyse the history of a site/landscape by using maps and aerial photos (+plans if found).
- Learn about and describe spatial (and landscape) change over time.

Learning activities and assessment

The whole exercise is supervised by teachers, in both finding material (mainly in online archives but occasionally in physical archives) and analysing it. The analysis is done in several different techniques (for example overlays and transfers of structures) in the studio, for the students to learn from each other and to get supervision by teachers at the drawing table. The analysis is done totally without computers. The presentation of the results is also an important learning activity, to get feedback on both the process and the results. The module is assessed based on a hand-in of overlays and transfers (or photographs of them), and an oral presentation are mandatory and are parts of the examination and assessment of the exercise.

Key advice for teachers

If the students do this for the first time, a manual on how to search for maps and aerial photos (and where) is crucial, as well as instructions for converting the scale and how to do overlays and transfers. Making short instruction videos of how to do overlays and transfers is worthwhile and appreciated by the students.

This exercise is best done by hand, with pen and paper, when doing it for the first time. This allows the students to get a muscle memory of the landscape structures, which is a way of learning that permits the knowledge and memory from the exercise to last longer.

For beginners, it is a good idea to show them the difference between doing one tracing per map and to do all the map overlays on the same tracing paper using different colours for each map/year. But we usually let the students decide how to proceed themselves – the results should be a visualisation of historical change either way.

Usually, aerial photos show more vegetation structures than maps and are therefore often best analysed by themselves. But since aerial photos do not go so far back in time, creating a timeline of overlays using both maps and aerial photos together in a mix is therefore a good idea when it comes to grasping the whole picture.

Using too much zoomed out maps is seldom a good idea when analysing sites in a smaller scale such as squares, residential areas or small parks. The aerial photos and the design plans are better sources there, and the choice of scale is of importance. But when including the maps, the students can grasp the bigger picture and see how the site is affected by changes around it over time.

When doing a transfer of structures (historical or new) onto an aerial photo, the aerial photo needs to be printed in a bright mode, for the transfer lines to be seen more clearly.

There is no need for the students to read a lot of literature to find out facts about why or how this certain landscape has changed. On the contrary, if they do this exercise without previous knowledge or preconceptions, they are open to a wider interpretation of the maps, plans and aerial photos.

Assignment

The total time scheduled for this is about 2-3 days; 1 day, partly supervised, to find and print maps/aerial photos, 1 day of studio work, doing analyses with supervision, and about half a day of presentations with feedback from teachers. The hand-in is done directly after the presentations.

1 Search

An important part of this exercise is to find maps, plans and aerial photos, from different archives and with a reasonable timespan from the earliest time there were any maps of that landscape until today, but not leaving too large time gaps. The students are usually short of time so many maps are retrieved via online archives, but plans are often retrieved from other archives at a later stage.

2 Print on scale

The maps and/or aerial photos are printed and copied (using the zoom-function) on the same scale. This takes some time and usually needs some calculation beforehand.

3 Analysis

The maps are analysed in the studio, doing overlays manually, without a computer. This is done either by tracing important structures (roads, vegetation, housing etc, whatever is being analysed) on one tracing paper per map and then laying all the tracing papers on top of each other and analysing the differences, OR by tracing important structures from each map on the same tracing paper, but with separate colours for each year in question.

4 Transfer

Transfers of certain historical structures from the analysis of the overlays are drawn onto an aerial photo from today using a light table. A transfer could also be done of a structure from today onto an old map or plan – in both cases the changes over time will be visualised.

5 Areas of interest

Finally, we encourage the students to mark certain areas of interest with circles and arrows and writing short descriptions of what the circles and arrows point at (a rapid change, an unchanged structure over time or something else they find interesting).

6 Present

They present the changes over time for this place/ landscape orally to other students, showing their manually drawn analyses on tracing paper. This allows them to talk about the process more than the finished product, to learn what colours are visible from afar and to describe their findings narratively in an efficient way without any pressure of it being too polished.

References

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Figure 9: The illustration shows overlays in a timeline-collection of blue lines from 5 different map and/or aerial photos of Malmö coastline, and a transfer of all of them onto an aerial photo from 2019. (Overlays and transfer: Simon Ljungström, student at SLU Alnarp, 2019. Aerial photo: copyright Lantmäteriet, Sweden. The illustration is used with the student's permission)

Urban and Architectural History II / Kent ve Mimarlık Tarihi II

Archival analysis

Urban Design and Landscape Architecture, 2nd year Bachelors

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Why teaching with archival materials?

This course provides an in-depth exploration of the spatial development of cities and architecture from the 19th century to the present day. It focuses on the intertwined evolution of social, political, and technological contexts that shaped urban forms and built environments. Archives serve as a crucial pedagogical tool to immerse students in original urban plans, detailed maps, historical photographs, governmental reports, and landscape design proposals related to city transformations. The primary aim is to significantly enhance students' ability to interpret, analyse, and critically evaluate historical documents. This allows them to forge direct connections between archival findings and the broader urban and architectural developments, including the evolution of urban green spaces, parks, and public landscapes. This archival approach cultivates a deeper understanding of how historical decisions and environmental considerations have shaped the cities and landscapes we inhabit today.

This archival research is a semester-long process systematically integrated into the assessment: the midterm exam focuses on research methodology and source identification, while the final exam evaluates the critical interpretation and spatial analysis of the archival evidence gathered throughout the term.

The archival material is used for the following reasons:

- Students learn to analyse primary sources not merely as illustrations but as spatial evidence. The goal is to train students to read historical documents to identify landscape features and urban configurations that are no longer visible in contemporary contexts.
- By comparing historical archival findings with current site conditions, students identify how urban and landscape forms have changed over time. This helps them understand the process of transformation as a central theme in landscape history.
- The course encourages students to independently search for, identify, and validate archival materials under instructor guidance. This builds baseline proficiency in navigating digital and physical repositories and teaches the importance of source criticism.
- By unearthing historical layers, students develop a deeper understanding of how past decisions shape the cities and landscapes we inhabit today. This perspective allows them to relate archival discoveries to current urban and environmental issues.

What will students learn?

- Analyse the historical evolution of cities and their landscapes within broader socio-political, economic, and technological contexts.
- Interpret a diverse range of archival materials, including maps, photographs, urban plans, and landscape designs.
- Develop critical perspectives on processes of urban transformation within historical contexts.
- Connect insights gained from archival research directly with contemporary urban and landscape design thinking and challenges.
- Communicate research findings effectively and professionally through both visual and written outputs.

Learning activities and assessment

Context is provided by lectures and guided discussions on key historical periods and theoretical frameworks. The urban history of Amasya is used as a model case study for in-depth research, leveraging various archives to demonstrate methodology. Groups of students analyse and interpret selected archival materials (maps, plans, photographs, reports) focusing on urban and landscape elements. Note: The selection of archival materials is a

collaborative and supervised process. Students conduct their own research to identify archival materials relevant to their selected city. The instructor then reviews these materials for suitability and provides additional suggestions or sources when necessary. Individual research support and guidance is provided asynchronously via online platforms (e.g., MS Teams) to assist students with archival access, source identification, and research challenges. Students trace changes in specific urban or landscape sites through comparative mapping exercises and visual documentation analyses. Finally, students present their findings on the selected cities, periods, or thematic urban/landscape transformations, based on their archival research.

Assessment focuses on the analysis of the Anatolian cities' spatial, architectural, and landscape transformations from the late Ottoman period to the present, the research methods employed, the resources utilized, and the specification of archives consulted.

Key advice for teachers

Begin by identifying manageable local archives or municipal collections that students can access either physically or through online platforms.

Provide clear and structured guidance on how to interpret both visual and textual archival materials effectively, emphasizing critical analysis through the following steps:

- Students are required to base their analysis strictly on the data provided within the archival document.
- Students identify the character of the landscape -whether it is 'sacred/untouchable,' 'monumental/authoritative,' or 'social/everyday'-by analysing the document type, architectural typologies, and the human activities or figures depicted.
- Students relate their historical findings to the present day by comparing archival data with contemporary site conditions, identifying how past spatial decisions continue to shape current urban and landscape challenges.

Encourage students to use their archival findings as a foundation for future-oriented design interventions, moving from historical analysis to creative problem-solving.

Assignment

1 Select

Students will select a specific urban context (a city or district) that experienced significant urban and/or landscape transformation within a defined historical period, focusing on a context relevant to the course's themes.

2 Search

Students independently search for and identify relevant archival materials -including historical maps, urban plans, landscape designs, photographs, and official reports- from local city archives or digital archives. To ensure research quality, the instructor acts as a facilitator by providing a curated list of reliable repositories and offering continuous guidance on source identification and access challenges throughout this process.

3 Describe

Document and contextualize the collected archival materials by creating a systematic inventory. For each item, describe its content, origin, date, and its potential relevance to the urban context under study.

4 Analyse

Analyse the historical materials to understand spatial, social, and environmental changes. Complement this analysis by comparing the historical archival documents with current maps, aerial photographs, or on-site observations to identify continuities and discontinuities, and specific areas of transformation on the ground.

5 Present

Develop a research poster that visually articulates the significant urban and/or landscape transformations identified through your archival work, supported by key historical evidence and your critical analysis.

References

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Figure 10: Pirlar Cemetery in Amasya, transformed into a park in the Early Republican Period.
© Prepared by Kalkan-Açikkapı (2019, 138) as adapted from 1: Ottoman Archives, OA, DH.MKT.PRK, 134/36, 2 Rebiülevvel 1287/June 2, 1870, accessed on August 1, 2018. Plan of Beyler Sarayı (in ruins), Sofular Neighbourhood. 2: Gabriel, A. (1934). *Monuments Turcs D'Anatolie, Tome Deuxième Amasya-Tokat-Sivas*. Paris: E. De Boccard.

Urbanism and Landscape Architecture Course

Art, Architecture, Media and Design, 2nd year Bachelors

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Why teaching with archival materials?

In the broad Bachelor programme, archival material is an important source for studying (landscape) architectural history. Students learn both to inform themselves about facts and meanings of historical projects and situations, to get insight in the diversity of historical sources and archival material (text, images and models), and to interpret these.

Get to know the differences between an original document and its reproduction. In this course only reproductions are shown.

What will students learn?

- Learn urban and landscape architecture history and meaning.
- Construct an overview, using literature on landscape architecture history and archival documents.

Learning activities and assessment

The lectures and seminars include demonstrations by the lecturer, a class exercise during seminar (interpretation of literature and historical images/archival material and current photographs), and group and individual writing exercises. It is assessed with a multiple-choice exam.

Key advice for teachers

Select a broad variety of relatively simple and easy to understand examples and a few complex ones to demonstrate that not all archival materials are that simple and clear.

Teach students both historical content (key examples, form, meaning, historical context) and tools to interpret archival documents (images) at the same time. Important questions are: why is this document created, for whom? What can we see, what not, and why? What is 'true', what not, and why?

Assignment

1 Active lecturing

The history demonstrated by lecturer is tested immediately by questions during class. For instance, before explaining that not all images (prints, paintings) represent the accurate situation on site, the lecturer asks what the students look at, what they think they see, possibly with some hints or keywords.

2 Study archival materials

In a class exercise students, in groups of 3 or 4, study (reproductions of) archival material based on the main themes of the lecture: people (society) and place; nature and culture (art and technology); city and countryside; physical and mental/ideological ordering of space (the definition of design used in the course). To recognise and explain the themes in preselected images.

3 Understand ideas

Goal of the exercise is to learn that both 'order' or geometry and 'naturalness' are the outcomes of deliberate design and reflect the human-nature relationship and ideas about 'naturalness' in a certain period. Students also learn that ideas about that relation change through history.

An example of an image is one of a series of prints of the estate of Heemstede (see added image): the axis and trimmed hedges as tools to create spatial order; the 'wooded' area behind the hedge represents the 'natural' growth of plants and emphasises the contrast between 'wildness' and order.

4 Understand images

Second purpose of the exercise: understand that historical images (like the plan and prints of Heemstede) are not entirely representing the landscape as it was but can be idealised. Designs were not always constructed as desired (because of lack of money, landscape conditions, conflicts, availability of materials etc), but images can depict them as if they were.

References

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Figure 11: Isaac de Moucheron - view from the 'star forest' toward the house at Heemstede estate 1706-1719 (Rijksmuseum Amsterdam). An example of Dutch baroque estate design, showing the contrast between order (geometry) and 'naturalness'.

Studio Site design Study archival materials

Landscape architecture, 2nd year Bachelor

Lisanne Struckman

Wageningen University & Research
The Netherlands

Why teaching with archival materials?

After a joint first year with spatial planning, this is the first full design studio (8 weeks) for landscape architecture students. The assignment is to redesign an existing urban park with a diversity of functions. In week 4, when the students start elaborating their spatial concept into a site plan on scale 1:500 with details 1:100/50, they visit the archive. Teachers show hand-drawn plans, sections and perspectives of designs from different periods for the following reasons:

- Learn about hand-drawn representation techniques. How to draw a plan, a section? How to draw trees, show height? In this stage of their studies, students haven't learnt yet how to draw digitally and draw everything by hand. Contemporary designs are almost exclusively digitally drawn, so archival material is needed to show hand-drawn representation techniques.
- Learn about form and composition in landscape design. For instance, carefully composing tree groups and creating perspectives with plantings instead of randomly scattering trees, or designing a winding path, not as a doodle but as a carefully designed, stylised form.
- Learn that context matters and must be included in the design drawings. For instance, a park that is surrounded by the backyards of houses is different from a park that is surrounded by busy roads, and requires different connections to the wider urban fabric.
- Learn about scale. Students must develop an understanding of what is drawn on which scale, why and how. Studying physical design drawings on their real scale does that, zooming in and out on a screen doesn't.
- Make students aware of the existence and availability of the archive and archival materials.

What will students learn?

- Students build a frame of reference of form and composition and of representation techniques. It helps them to achieve the following learning objectives of the design studio:
 - Design a selected spatial concept into a master plan and refine the design solutions into a detailed design,
 - Apply basic level visualization techniques.

Learning activities and assessment

Teachers show and explain original plans and drawings in the archives of Special Collections of Wageningen University & Research. Assessment is summative, not formal. Teachers will refer to the examples shown in the archive while tutoring the design phase.

Key advice for teachers

Most archives have limited space to welcome people. Often, a group of students must be split into smaller groups.

It is good to discuss with the archivists not only the drawings you would like to show to the students, but also why you want to show them, the learning objectives. Archivists know their collections and may come up with relevant additional or alternative materials.

It is important to explicitly refer in tutoring sessions in the design phase to the materials students have seen. The visit to the archive is not a random nice visit, it is part of the learning process.

It is good to show and discuss drawings from different periods that include different ideas of what an urban park is or could be. Showing a variety of conceptual ideas, styles, and drawing techniques will broaden the students' frame of reference and inspire them to look beyond what they already know.

In addition to the final drawings and plans, the teacher can also show sketches that precede the final design drawings. Sketches show that a design is not 'just drawn' but it preceded by a design process in which different options are explored and step by step elaborated in detail.

Assignment

1 Preparation (teachers)

The teacher selects materials in collaboration with the archivists. As shown in the description, there are multiple reasons for the archival visit. Teacher and archivist select the drawings that enable the teacher to discuss the topics he/she wants to.

2 Archival visit (students and teachers)

The teacher shows the archival materials to the students, explaining the relevant aspects and discusses them with the students. Students to actively engage with the materials by questions of the teachers.

3 Apply in design studio (students and teachers)

Students apply the examples shown in the archive in their design. Teachers will refer to the examples shown and topics discussed during the archival visits in tutoring.

4 Build frame of reference (students)

By explicitly referring to the examples from the archives and applying them, they will become part of students' frame of reference for future use.

Selected references

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Figures 12 and 13: The images show an example of archival material shown to the students (Springer 1888, design Rijsterborcherpark Deventer), and an example of a student design (Marissa van Ooijen, 2024) that used the lessons from the archival visit.

History of landscape architecture Course

Landscape Architecture, 2nd year Bachelors

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Why teaching with archival materials?

This course introduces the historical development of gardens, open spaces, and plant use from Antiquity to the modern period, enabling students to understand gardens not only as formal compositions but also as cultural expressions shaped by their historical contexts. Major historical periods are addressed with particular attention to spatial organisation, relationships with nature, and plant use.

A central component of the course is the critical examination of the sources through which knowledge of historical landscapes has been transmitted. Students are introduced to a range of archival and representational materials in order to recognise that landscape history is largely constructed through documentary evidence.

The archival component focuses specifically on Ottoman sharia court registers, which are accessible through transcriptions. These official records document civil and administrative matters and contain detailed property descriptions referring to gardens, courtyards, open spaces, and occasionally plants. They provide valuable insight into everyday residential environments, extending students' understanding beyond the monumental and elite landscapes that typically dominate landscape history.

Using court records from Trabzon - the city in which the students live - enables students to establish a direct relationship between archival data and their immediate surroundings. By extracting basic spatial and botanical information from the records and comparing these findings with contemporary gardens, students develop an awareness of cultural continuity and change. This approach helps students internalise the core themes of the course and recognise the connection between historical knowledge and professional practice.

Through this process, archives are presented not only as historical sources but also as practical tools that support students' developing knowledge of plant use, spatial analysis, and landscape interpretation.

What will students learn?

- Recognize that knowledge of landscape architectural history is produced through archival sources.
- Become aware of different types of sources used in landscape history.
- Identify that archival documents such as Sharia court registers contain information on open spaces, gardens, and plants.
- Understand how such information can provide a foundation for plant, design, and analysis courses.
- Realize that basic spatial and botanical information can be extracted from historical documents.
- Compare historical and contemporary gardens.

Learning activities and assessment

Students get a brief introduction to what Sharia court registers are and how they can be read.

A sample archival document is collectively examined in the classroom to identify information related to gardens, open spaces, and plants in selected records. The extracted information is organised in simple lists or diagrams. Next, contemporary gardens are observed in the local environment, and historical and contemporary data are compared, followed by a short evaluation. Student performance is assessed through a general written exam on course topics, in addition to a written assignment that includes a plant list, photographs, and a comparative analysis.

Key advice for teachers

For instructors who wish to use archives in similar courses, it is recommended to select readable archival sources appropriate to the students' level and closely related to the local context as an introductory approach. It is important that archival work supports the main themes of the course and produces concrete outcomes that students can apply in other courses.

Assignment

1 Preparation (teachers)

Preparation is minimal. The instructor selects suitable transcribed court records and provides a short introduction during class. Students require no prior archival knowledge.

2 Introduction to the archival source

A brief explanation is given on what Sharia court registers are, what kind of information they contain, and why they are used in this course.

3 Selection of documents

Transcribed Sharia court registers from Trabzon are provided, and appropriate documents are selected for the assignment.

4 Identification of open space and garden information

References to gardens, courtyards, and open spaces are identified within the selected records.

5 Extraction of botanical data

Plant-related information mentioned in the documents is identified and compiled into a simple plant list.

6 Organization of spatial information

Information related to gardens and open spaces is organized in the form of short notes or simple diagrams.

7 Observation of the contemporary environment

Students observe gardens in their immediate surroundings and record their main characteristics.

8 Comparison

Historical data derived from the records are compared with contemporary observations.

9 Reporting

The findings are presented in a written report including the plant list, visual material, and a brief comparative evaluation.

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Turkish

...mahalle-i mezbûrede vâki'bir taraftan Derzî Hüseyin mülkü ve bir taraftan Debbâğ İbrahim mülkü ve bir taraftan Sarrâç Ali mülkü ve bir taraftan tarîk-i 'âmm ile mahdûd bir bâb beyt-i suflî ve havlûyu ve bir kenîf ve iki sâk zeytûn eşcârını ve sâ'ir eşcârı müsmire ve gayr-ı müsmireli bağçeyi nısfı bi'r-i mâ'iyi müştemil mülk menzîlimizi cemî'-i müştemilâtıyla...

English

The property, located in the same neighbourhood, is bounded on one side by the property of Derzî Hüseyin (tailor), on another by the property of Debbâğ İbrahim (tanner), on another by the property of Sarraç Ali (saddler), and on the remaining side by a public road. **The estate consists of a lower house with a courtyard, a privy, two olive trees, other fruit-bearing and non-fruit-bearing trees, and half of a garden, together with all its appurtenances.**

Figure 14: From left to right: general view of an original sharia court register, its transcription, and an olive tree in Trabzon. Prepared by the author (2025, Abdullah Çiğdem)

Research seminar Architecture Research seminar

Architectural History 3rd year Bachelors

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Why teaching with archival materials?

In architectural history, students must learn to find archival material as one of the sources to study. They need to learn how to use archival material and get to know its benefits and limits compared to other sources. Archival research is the base to write or revise (landscape) architectural history and present it to peers.

What will students learn?

- Conduct architectural historical research (on a theme selected by the lecturer, varying every year – this example: designs for Floriade – horticultural - exhibits).
- Critically analyze and interpret design concepts and discourses, urbanism and landscape architecture and to place these designs, concepts and discourses in a historical context.
- Research and interpret historical and contemporary written sources and archival documents.
- Understand that history is a construction, a 'story' based on a selection of facts, materials and spatial elements.
- Present academic research orally to peers.

Learning activities and assessment

The research seminar includes lectures and seminars with active participation. Field trip(s) to projects (Floriade Venlo 2012) and archival institutions (city and provincial archives) are part of it. Archival materials on Floriade exhibitions are used in all activities.

During the seminars the students' choice of topic, research question, choice of sources and research methods are discussed in class and commented by the lecturer before they individually finish their paper. The final assessment is based on an oral presentation and a final written paper. The assessment of the use of archival material in the final paper firstly depends on the research question: is the choice of sources sufficient and appropriate? Are the materials interpreted adequately to answer the research question?

Key advice for teachers

Before giving students the option to choose a topic (within the collective theme of a seminar), demonstrate clearly what the possibilities and limits of studying archives as an optional historical source are; for instance, archival research is very inspiring and can generate rich materials, but it also can be time consuming and complicated to interpret the finds.

Another pitfall can be that a student is not able to find anything. This can be discussed in a seminar meeting, asking the group how to solve the issue before the lecturer gives specific directions: let the students think for themselves before offering a solution.

It is therefore best to choose a theme and clearly delimit the topic and limit the research to a selected archival collection; the lecturer needs to do preliminary research to be sure that there is enough and diverse archival material for the group of students.

Assignment

1 Introduction of topic and research methods

Introduction of the general history and context of the topic (world exhibitions) by the lecturer;
Lecturer demonstrates methods of research, such as literature study, archival research, on site analysis.

2 Collective study

Collective study of basic information (contemporary and historical texts and images, archival material) and state of research; feedback by students.

3 Visit site and archives

Collective site visit to study and experience a built horticultural exhibition, following guidelines and questions prepared by the lecturer. Archival visits are individual, based on the students' topics. Progress is discussed collectively and in tutorials.

4 Present topic and approach

Students present a topic of choice and their approach. For instance: assessment of the ambitions of the municipality of Haarlemmermeer for Floriade 2002 and the redevelopment of the grounds afterward; designs and transition of the grounds of Floriade 1960 in Rotterdam, before, during and after the exhibition; typological comparison between Floriade exhibitions and theme park designs.

5 Interim report and peer review

Interim reports by students and peer reviews.

6 Products

Final research papers by individual students, including acknowledgement of archival materials used and their location.

References

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Figure 15: Flowerbeds and cableway at Floriade Rotterdam, 1960. Wikimedia Commons

Lecture critique de réalisations / Critical reading of completed works

Exercise

Landscape architecture, 3rd year Bachelors

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France

Why teaching with archival materials?

- BSc 3 Semester 1 design studios includes “An urban district”. Semester 2 design studio is focused on: “What Park for XXIst century?”. They are prepared and nourished by a history course and visits about Urban Open Space History and this tutorial exercise about a selection of completed works built up through XXth century. Students use archives to reconstruct the stages of a designed place, starting from the current situation backwards to the original site.

What will students learn?

- Students learn to decipher a completed project through a multiscale approach, which involves buildings and open spaces at different scales of space and time. Reconstructing the landscape dimension history is a more difficult task than finding architectural elements. It concerns XXth century public parks and housing district explored as possible references:
 - Describe the current situation,
 - Understand the steps of making and the different people involved,
 - Figure out the link between a given period of time and the landscape production,
 - Understand the complexity of filling in “the white or green in the maps”, “the unfigured” of open spaces.

Learning activities and assessment

It often involves threatened places where landscape dimension is overlooked, or possible 20th century heritage. 2 or 3 different sites are proposed by the teaching team (i.e. a garden city, a postwar housing estate and a recent eco-district, all connected with or including a park) students will chose a site, a place to focus and a theme of analysis. As it is often an unrepresented part of our living space or a side element of different projects you need to explore and gather several sources of information or types of archives. Sharing the findings of the different groups with the whole class will contribute to building a territorial frame of all the projects studied, a local analysis for each and a possible hypothesis about the “writing “, the design of a place.

The exercise involves creating a portfolio combining reflections, texts, and graphic production (cross-sections, sketches, site plans, ground plans) in the form of an A3 vertical Chinese notebook. The grading is based on the historical dimension and archival research: presentation, titles, respect of assignment (25%), history and use of archives (25%), critical reading, consistency, argumentation (25%) and graphical production 25%.

Key advice for teachers

Students do not have time (and skills) to search themselves for the archives so you will have previously gathered the archives files in order to provide them for the students. You will explain where they come from and how you have collected them. If they are interested, a few of them may have access to the original archives, but you need to plan it with them and accompany them. (for us, this is on their and our “free” time).

Assignment

1 Preparation (teachers)

Select sites (if possible consistent with design studio) and make a preliminary site visit (1 day). Gather the material about the sites and identify existing archives (and new ones to explore). Contact people involved in original design and current maintenance.

2 Retro-prospective description in space and time (1st semester)

- Analytical report of site visits, identification of points of interest. Notes drawn in sketches, sections and plans. Keywords.
- Choose a thematic question and one of the places visited (group work).
- Make a roadmap to explore the question issues, sections, plans, or other drawings.

3 Research and report (2nd semester)

- Research archival documents and produce draft analysis documents with surveys and diachronic representation. Prepare on site work with archives, appointments in archives center are proposed specifically when new sites are addressed.
- Return to site
- Create a Chinese notebook: make a “flat-plan”, develop the layout and produce graphic and written content.
- Final presentation and synthesis of different groups.

References

André Corboz (1995) La description entre lecture et écriture, in: *Le territoire comme palimpseste et autres essais*, Les éditions de l'Imprimeur, 2002, pp. 249-257.

Books about the studied sites such as:

Elise Guillerm (2022), *Une Cité-jardin Moderne. La Butte Rouge à Chatenay Malabry*, Parenthèses, Marseille.

Blanchon, Bernadette (2026), The potential of scholarly reading of constructed landscapes. Or the difficult art of interpretation, *JoLA*, 2-2026, (anniversary issue), p. 66-71.

Blanchon B. (2019) Teaching the history of urban open space using a multiscale approach, in Jorgensen K., Karadeniz N., Stiles R. & Mertens E. (Eds.,2019), *Teaching Landscape, the studio experience*, London, ECLAS-Routledge, p. 230-249.

Blanchon B. (2013) Critical readings: changing approaches and interests in Landscape education, *Landscape and Imagination. Towards a new baseline for education in a changing world* (conference proceedings), Pisa, Bandechi & Vivaldi, p. 375-380.

Figure 16: Extracts of students' production in 2023-24 about the Garden City of La Butte Rouge, Chatenay-Malabry (92) south of Paris (70 ha, 3700 housing Units, 1931-1965) [see: *Landscape Architecture and Infrastructure of the twentieth century, Docomomo*, 2024, p. 46-48], DEP.2, M1, ENSP. "Water and soil treatment at La butte Rouge", Ryan Ajanou, Juliette Biree, Tristan Leiva-Marcon & Marion Nader, 2023, p. 4-5 et 14-17. "La Butte Rouge, a garden city between town and forest, Corentin Baret, Christopher Doche, Séraphin Mallié, Benjamin Mann, 2023, p. 17.

History of Ideas in Landscape Architecture and Planning Excursion with archival visit

Landscape Architecture and Planning 3rd year Bachelors

Wim Bosschaart

Wageningen University & Research
The Netherlands

Why teaching with archival materials?

The course is a third year BSc course on how societal ideas (over time) have shaped the course of planning and landscape architecture and how, in turn, these plans and practices have influenced societal ideas and debates.

After a series of lectures on the historical development of both disciplines, students embark on a foreign excursion and explore which historic traces are still visible today.

Archives are an important information source for students, and in this course, we want to further encourage them to use these archives (for example, in their assignments and/or future bachelor thesis research).

What will students learn?

- Assess the relationship between historical and contemporary design and planning theories, examining how these theories manifest in real landscapes by providing fieldwork analyses.
- Understand plans and designs in their time-space context, surpassing the level of easily made and superficial judgements.
- Understand the ideas and deliberation behind these plans, particular the motivation.

Learning activities and assessment

The course includes lectures, exercises and a foreign excursion. The exercise discussed here is part of an archival visit and consists of remaking a photo, observations, street interviews, supplementary (archive) material, etc. The information is submitted using a sheet and assessed in a formative way, on site and afterwards.

Key advice for teachers

Make the use of archives more alive and fun, for example, by using an assignment as presented above, as some/most students still have a preconceived notion of archives being dull. However, these exercises show the richness of the material, its added value and even the fun of discovering bits and pieces of the past, often beyond the students' initial imagination. It also helps to team up with enthusiastic archival staff, who can further demonstrate the added value of archives. And lastly, actively encourage students to use archives as resource, for example, by stimulating archival visit for a number of times.

Assignment

1 Archival visit

The students visited Crawley museum, together with students of University of Brighton. Lectures and curators gave a brief history of the New Towns movement in the UK and how this played out in Crawley. Thereafter, an archivist of the West Sussex Archive in Chichester talked about archiving plans, photos, correspondence, etc. around the development of these New Towns and the importance of this information repository for researchers. Students were introduced in what archives are for, what information to find there and how to extract this, applied to the Crawley case.

2 Photo exhibition

The students visited the museum, both the permanent collection on New Towns (including the original plan) as well as the temporary exhibition on photographs that were made right after the development of Crawley New Town by photographer and WWII-refugee Wolf Suschitzky.

3 Remake photograph

Students (in groups) were given a copy of one of these pictures from 1959 and were tasked to locate the photo in the current town and do 'remake' photograph.

4 Compare

Students were challenged to compare the ideas/ideals of the New Towns back then with the reality of the current New Town. Which ideals are still visible, which not? What has changed and why so? Also, students are encouraged to conduct short street interviews and observations on site, to support their analysis.

References

Winkler, J. (2025). *Crawley New Town seen through the lens of Wolf Suschitzky*. Exhibition catalogue.

Figure 17: Wolf Suschitzky, Tilgate Shopping Arcade, 1959. Courtesy Fotohof Salzburg/Copyright Suschitzky/Donat Family.

Studio DOCOMOMO Design studio

Architecture, 4th year Bachelor

Igor Kuvač

University of Banja Luka
Bosnia and Herzegovina

Why teaching with archival materials?

Studio DOCOMOMO was organized on the occasion of establishing DOCOMOMO Bosnia and Herzegovina, the national branch of the international organization dedicated to documenting, protecting, and promoting Modern Movement architecture. The studio aimed to introduce students to the architectural, cultural, ideological, and political context of socialist Yugoslavia and to explore proactive approaches for protecting modern heritage through contemporary narratives.

Archival materials formed the foundation of both pedagogical and research objectives. Students worked with original documentation from the Archives of the Republic of Srpska, the Archives of the City of Banja Luka, the Institute for Construction, and the Urban Institute to build a comprehensive digital database of modern architecture in Banja Luka. Archives enabled students to reconstruct historical contexts, analyse value systems of the second half of the 20th century, digitally reconstruct endangered or vanished buildings, and develop a structured heritage valorization system. Authentic archival sources, combined with collected memories, supported the construction of narratives for 15 individual buildings, mapping physical space, social space, and values as components of collective memory and urban identity.

What will students learn?

- Knowledge:
 - Understand architectural and urban heritage within theoretical and institutional frameworks, including DOCOMOMO methodologies,
 - Know heritage valorization principles across physical, social, and cultural dimensions,
 - Be aware of multidisciplinary approaches to heritage interpretation and adaptive re-use.
- Skills:
 - Conduct archival research and develop structured digital databases,
 - Do a critical heritage analysis using multidisciplinary tools,
 - Make digital reconstruction based on archival documentation,
 - Create spatial narratives using multimedia tools (video, audio, VR),
 - Map heritage integrating spatial, social, and value-based data.
- Competences:
 - Engage communities through participatory and co-creation methods,
 - Develop cultural programming concepts for heritage activation,
 - Be able to collaborate interdisciplinary and communicate with the public.

Learning activities and assessment

The semester-long studio integrated archival research sessions at heritage institutions, guest lectures by international experts, fieldwork documenting 15 modernist buildings, and community engagement through interviews and surveys. Students developed digital reconstructions, multimedia narratives, and mapping exercises through collaborative workshops. Archival research was continuously revisited and translated into creative narratives, small-scale interventions, and the preparation of a multimedia exhibition, including a VR corner and audio-guided urban walk. Iterative review sessions with faculty and partner organizations supported reflection and synthesis.

Assessment evaluated the use and interpretation of archival materials, including the quality of research documentation portfolios, accuracy of digital reconstructions, comprehensiveness of heritage mapping, and the

ability to translate archival knowledge into narratives and design concepts. Additional criteria included evidence of community engagement, innovation and feasibility of proposals, process documentation, critical thinking, and effectiveness of public presentation during the final exhibition opening on Youth Day (former Yugoslav holiday on May 25, 2022).

Key advice for teachers

Teachers are advised to establish early institutional collaboration with archives and partner organizations and to clearly structure archival access and guidance. Archives should be positioned as primary sources, distinct from literature and field observations, and integrated throughout the semester. Open-ended outcomes beyond conventional design projects are encouraged, including exhibitions, multimedia formats, and public events. Facilitating intergenerational dialogue, leveraging attachment to time and place, and connecting local research to international heritage frameworks are essential for archival engagement and long-term impact.

Assignment

The course was structured as a multi-phase research and design process centred on the parallel analysis of 15 selected modernist buildings from the second half of the 20th century. Students worked in small groups of 2–3, with every group responsible for one building, while individual tasks (archival research, field recording, digital modelling, mapping, and narrative construction) were clearly distributed to ensure both collective responsibility and individual contribution.

1 Time frame

The process began with time attachment and heritage recording, encouraging students to establish a personal connection with the period of socialist Yugoslavia through the collection of memories, buildings, places, and everyday artefacts using emotionally expressive media (photography, video, audio, drawing).

Figure 18: Studio DOCOMOMO exhibition opening on the date of Yugoslavian holiday, The Youth Day, May 25, 2022. The predominant section of the image encompasses a curated selection of digitized projects drawn from the archival documentation of modernist buildings in Banja Luka.

2 Archival research

This was followed by archival research, involving visits to archives, urban and construction institutes to collect planning documentation, architectural drawings, photographs, and historical records.

3 Digital reconstruction

Based on the collected material, students conducted digital reconstruction, including measured drawings, photographic documentation, digitisation of archival sources, and 3D modelling of existing, endangered, or vanished structures.

4 Representation

Heritage mapping synthesised findings into integrated representations of physical space, social space (documents, narratives, objects), and value systems across past–present–future timelines.

5 Alternative narratives

Through community engagement, students carried out participatory research with citizens connected to the buildings, using interviews and questionnaires. These inputs informed the construction of alternative narratives, translating archival knowledge and personal memories into multimedia stories (video, audio, VR, graphics).

6 Products

The process culminated in creative programme development, proposing contemporary uses and small-scale interventions, and a public multimedia exhibition featuring DOCOMOMO boards, a VR corner, and an audio-guided urban walk. Regular reviews, workshops, and mentoring sessions ensured continuous feedback, iterative development, and coherence across all case studies, resulting in a collective yet differentiated body of work.

References

- Богдановић, Б. (1982) *Градословар*. Београд: Вук Караџић.
- Radović, R. (1995) *Vrt ili kavez, eseji i studije arhitekture i grada*. Novi Sad: Prometej.
- Najdhart, J. i Grabrijan, D. (1957) *Arhitektura Bosne i put u savremeno*. Ljubljana: Državna založba Slovenije.
- Stierli, M., Mrduljaš, M. (2018) *Toward a Concrete Utopia. Architecture in Yugoslavia, 1948–1980*. New York: MoMA.
- Štraus, I. (1998) *Arhitektura Bosne i Hercegovine 1945-1995*. Sarajevo: Grafičko-izdavačka kuća d.d.

History of Landscape Architecture Exercise

Urbanism & Landscape Architecture, minor and pre-master

Imke van Hellemond

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The Netherlands

Why teaching with archival materials?

Getting familiar with a variety of archival documents is essential to understand that they are key to interpret, restore or redesign of historical and current sites.

What will students learn?

- Through the combination of history lectures, excursions and design exercises, from a historian and a landscape architect, students get a basic overview over design history and typology, learn to recognize historical elements and phases on site and are trained to apply this knowledge in design.
- Get a basic understanding of the history of landscape architecture in the Netherlands and its international context; spatially, stylistically and culturally.
- Learn to compare current and historical site qualities and analyse historical designs.
- Get to know the differences between an original document and its reproduction.
- Understand that a site's history is continuously changing through interventions, it cannot be reduced to one moment or period.
- Learn that the observation of a site on one specific moment is a clip from a dynamic process, caused by changes in weather, moment of the day, seasons.
- Learn to understand and analyse spatial and historical layering; connect the current situation of a site to prior situations, identify elements that disappeared and that are still there.
- Understand the difference between historical study from a historical and from a design perspective: history as a goal and history as an instrument to apply in current projects.
- Understand that history is a construction, a 'story' based on a selection of facts, materials and spatial elements.

Learning activities and assessment

Lectures on landscape architecture history present an overview of international (mainly western) history with a focus on the Netherlands, to give the students a general reference frame. For excursions and exercises three projects in Amsterdam are selected, from the 18th, 19th and 20th century: the estate of Frankendael, Rijksmuseum gardens and two parks (Thijssepark and Gijsbrecht van Aemstelpark). The archival materials offered as preparation for the site visits and the onsite experiences are used as a starting point for the design exercises. The course starts with knowledge building and ends with training of skills. Assessment is based on discussion, site exercises, and class drawing analysis.

Key advice for teachers

Stimulate the student's autonomous thinking and observation during the three different educational phases (lecture, excursion, design) to build experience and confidence: what do you see, think, feel? It is important to stress that thinking loudly and discussing personal observations is a way to learn.

Emphasize that to understand a site's history and current state, it is key to separate basic facts and knowledge from interpretation (arguments and value judgements).

Offer a frame or structure for students to deal with both the overload of facts and images in historical knowledge (periods, typologies, forms, materials) and the many spatial impressions during site visits (contours, levels, scale, materials, main elements, built and unbuilt).

Assignment

The essence of the exercise is that students do not gather or study information beforehand, but learn by observation and questioning on site.

1 Introduction and observation

After a short introduction on the sites (Frankendael estate, Rijksmuseum gardens, Thijssepark and Gijsbrecht van Aemstelpark) students conduct a site analysis in two groups, one led by a landscape architect, the other by a landscape architecture historian. The students in the 'historical' group identify their first impression, then establish the main historical elements and moments or periods of intervention and relate it to the lectures on landscape architecture history.

2 Analysis

After that, they answer questions about:

- the main style characteristics,
- the historical spatial relationship of the location of the project ('then and now' question),

- the difference between 'authentic' historical garden elements and materials and reconstructions,
- historical layering: all projects were built and restored in different periods,
- the typology (estate, now public garden; museum garden as an open-air museum room, celebrating Dutch national history; public parks in different urban contexts and styles).

3 The use of archival material

The lecturer brings reproductions of archival documents (maps, plans, drawings and photographs) to use as reference material after the first round of observation by the students. They learn which questions can be answered using archival documents and which not.

References

Horn, S., Rombout, S. (2013) De Rijksmuseumtuin – de complexiteit van een levend monument, *Cascade bulletin voor tuinhistorie* (2013), 22-2, pp. 49-56.

Figure 19: Plan of the garden and surroundings of the Rijksmuseum in Amsterdam, 1912. A set of plans, drawings and photographs is used to determine 19th century references to the 17th century, 19th century elements and 21st century re-interpretations of the 19th century garden. *Genootschap Architectura et Amicitia, Architectura*, 20 (1912) 33, p. 272.

Redesigning an Existing Project Using Archival Insights Workshop

Landscape architecture and related fields, Bachelors/Masters

Laura Jeschke & Maria João Fonseca

Universidad Rey Juan Carlos URJC Madrid & HTC-CFE, NOVA University Lisbon
Spain & Portugal

Why teaching with archival materials?

This workshop introduces students to the use of archival material in landscape architecture through a practical exercise based on a real-life example. The first part involves analysing the existing situation and defining an assessment and vision for the restoration or redesign of the existing project. In the subsequent part, students analyse the archival materials and, by engaging with the original planning documents and documentation, develop a deeper understanding of, and appreciation for, the historical project under study. Archival work should be internalised as part of the planning process in landscape architecture.

What will students learn?

- Identify and interpret diverse archival sources (plans, sketches, photographs, correspondence, oral histories, and selected secondary materials) using visual, spatial, conceptual, and relational methods.
- Understand the underlying history of the place to design interventions more connected to the site's specific identity.
- Develop critical skills by working with archival material, such as comparing sources and interpreting different levels of information.
- Learn from precedents by understanding ecological, social, and cultural values, as well as the design trends that shaped the original project.

Learning activities and assessment

The 100-120 minutes workshop, organised as a hands-on, collaborative group exercise, can be integrated into Design Studio or Landscape History classes and is suitable for both Bachelor's and Master's-level students. Participants work with curated sets of current materials (e.g., Google Earth images and documents from geoinformation platforms), archival sources (plans, sketches, notes and photographs), as well as selected secondary sources, including interviews, for a case study project.

Following a brief introduction to the exercise, students receive a historical overview of the existing project, focusing on its significance, original intent, and notable design features. To foster creative thinking and critical skills, it is important to avoid revealing excessive specific detail.

Assessment in this workshop is formative and relies on participants' active engagement. Students are evaluated on their contribution to group work and their ability to critically review archival documents and connect them to the task of restoring or carefully redesigning an existing project.

Feedback is provided orally by peers and professors during the final presentation and group discussion. A matrix based on the learning goals helps with evaluation.

Key advice for teachers

Choose a case study for which a variety of archival material is available, such as plans, drawings of different stages of the design process, correspondence, plant lists, photographs, tendering documents, and videos. Additionally, consider using secondary sources, such as magazines or book publications. Ideally, the project should be located in the city and known to students, or they should be able to visit it.

Current information on the project area, such as plan drawings and aerial views, should be provided at the same scale as the archive drawings. Materials, especially plan drawings and aerial views, should be printed at full size for the workshop.

Assignment

1 Introduction and historical context (5 min.)

Explanation of the exercise and a brief historical overview of the project, without too much detail.

2 Group formation (5 min.)

Divide students into groups of 3-5.

3 Initial proposal development (20 min.)

Based on the current situation, groups brainstorm and develop an initial design proposal for the project:

- What design elements are important to retain?
- How could the project be updated or adapted for contemporary use?
- What modern needs or priorities should be addressed in the proposal?

Focus on suggestions to emphasise sustainability, community engagement, or other points informing their proposals.

4 Review of archival documents (10 min.)

Each group is provided with a selection of archival documents related to the original project. Groups should analyse the provided materials to understand the original design intent and elements:

- What insights do these documents provide about the original project?
- Are there design elements that should be preserved or highlighted in their revised proposal?

5 Final proposal refinement (20 min.)

Using insights from the archival materials, each group refines its initial proposal.

- How does their revised plan incorporate or respond to the historical context?
- Are there elements from the original design they would adjust or preserve?
- How do they envision integrating modern uses while respecting the site's history?

6 Group presentations of revised proposals (2 min./group)

Focus on key changes made based on the archival materials.

7 Collective reflection (10 min.)

- What were the most relevant or surprising insights you gained from the archival material?
- What additional material would be interesting to continue the development of your project?
- What aspects of the original project did they find most influential?
- How can archives provide valuable insights for future design decisions?
- Why are archival materials important, or why choose to use them?

References

As sources for workshop materials, local archives with landscape architecture collections are consulted.

Figure 20: Results of group work with archival material for the redesign of Torre Picasso Gardens (1988) by landscape architect Leandro Silva Delgado and Olivais Norte (1964) by landscape architect Álvaro Ponce Dentinho, elaborated by students of Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Madrid, and Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Lisbon, in a collaborative hybrid workshop, May 2025.

Architettura del Paesaggio/ Landscape architecture Design studio + Drawing exercise

Architecture, 1st year Masters

Giulia Annalinda Neglia

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Why teaching with archival materials?

This exercise focused on the survey and analysis of the historical gardens and parks of Apulia within the Landscape Architecture course at the 4th year of the Master Degree in Architecture. During the exercise, students explored the spatial, botanical, and cultural characteristics of these sites, documenting their design principles, plant compositions, stylistic characteristics and historical evolution. The activity combined on-site observation with archival research, encouraging students to interpret the relationship between heritage landscapes and contemporary planning.

The aim of the exercise was to develop a critical understanding of how historical gardens.

The activity emphasized the integration of historical knowledge with contemporary landscape architecture practices, fostering an understanding of heritage as a dynamic resource for sustainable design. The creation of archives responds to the urgent need to preserve and disseminate knowledge about Apulian historical gardens and landscapes, which are often vulnerable to neglect, urbanization, and climate change. By compiling systematic documentation—plans, photographs, plant inventories, and historical references—students contributed to a shared repository that can support research, conservation, and adaptive reuse. This initiative underscores the role of archives as tools for safeguarding cultural identity and promoting informed decision-making in landscape planning.

This module emphasizes the importance of documentation as a tool for safeguarding cultural landscapes and integrating them into sustainable design strategies.

What will students learn?

- Ability to conduct field surveys and interpret historical landscape features.
- Skills in archival research and digital documentation.
- Understanding of the cultural, ecological, and aesthetic values of historical gardens.
- Competence in analyzing spatial organization, plant species, and stylistic elements.
- Awareness of conservation challenges and strategies for heritage landscapes.

Learning activities and assessment

Students will:

- Choose a historical garden or park in Apulia.
- Perform an on-site survey, including mapping, photographic documentation, and plant identification.
- Research historical sources (plans, texts, iconography) to reconstruct the garden's evolution.
- Produce an analytical report combining field data and archival material.
- Upload findings to a shared digital archive for future academic and professional use.
- Design a park or a garden connected to the historical one.

Student performance in this module is assessed through a combination of continuous evaluation and final project submission, focusing on both process and outcomes. Evaluation emphasizes methodological rigor, critical analysis, and technical accuracy rather than mere descriptive work. Students are encouraged to demonstrate interdisciplinary thinking and originality in interpreting historical landscapes. Feedback is provided throughout the process to support iterative improvement.

The assessment criteria include:

- Fieldwork and Data Collection (accuracy and completeness of on-site survey, including mapping, photographic documentation, and plant identification),
- Archival Research (depth and relevance of historical sources consulted, and ability to integrate archival material into the analysis),
- Presentation, Discussion and Final Project Submission (effectiveness in communicating findings during the final presentation, demonstrating critical thinking and engagement with heritage conservation and connection to landscape design issues).

Key advice for teachers

Establish clear and standardized guidelines for data collection to ensure consistency and comparability.

Incorporate digital tools for mapping and archiving to enhance accessibility and long-term usability. Foster collaboration with local institutions (municipal archives, heritage offices) to enrich resources and validate historical data.

Promote interdisciplinary approaches, integrating history, botany, and design analysis for a holistic understanding.

Emphasize the practical relevance of archives for conservation and planning, motivating students to view their work as impactful beyond the classroom.

Assignment

Students will document and analyze the spatial, botanical, and historical characteristics of a selected historical garden or park in Apulia, contributing their findings to a shared digital archive.

1 Site Selection

Choose a historical garden or park in Apulia from the list provided or propose one for approval.

2 Preliminary Research

Gather basic information about the site: location, historical context, ownership, and accessibility.

3 Field Survey

Conduct an on-site visit to perform detailed mapping, photographic documentation, and plant species identification. Record spatial organization and key design features.

4 Archival Investigation

Consult historical sources (plans, iconography, texts) from local archives, libraries, or online repositories to reconstruct the garden's evolution.

5 Data Organization

Compile field notes, photographs, and archival materials into a structured format (maps, tables, annotated images) provided by the instructor.

6 Analytical Report

Prepare a written report based on a provided file.

7 Digital Archive Contribution

Upload all documentation (report, images, maps, and metadata) to the course's shared digital platform following the provided guidelines.

8 Presentation and Discussion

Present findings in class, highlighting key insights and proposing strategies for heritage conservation and adaptive reuse.

References

- Cazzato, V., & Mantovano, A. (2010). *Giardini di Puglia. Paesaggi storici fra natura e artificio fra utile e diletto*. Lecce: Mario Congedo Editore.
- Manganelli Del Fà, R., Casciani, A., Vettori, S., et al. (2022). Sustainable conservation and restoration of historical gardens. In *Handbook of Cultural Heritage Analysis* (pp. 1745–1762). Springer.
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- Regione Puglia. (2015). *Piano Paesaggistico Territoriale Regionale (PPTR): Gargano – Paesaggio*. Bari: Regione Puglia.
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Architecture, Cities, Landscapes: Research Seminar

Research seminar

Architectural History, 1st year Masters

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Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
The Netherlands

Why teaching with archival materials?

The research seminar is a preparation for the individual research process of the Master Thesis.

- Learn to autonomously find and use archival material as one of the sources to study, write or revise (landscape) architectural history and present it to peers
- Apply the results of archival research in a sophisticated way and at an academic level
- Augment the awareness of the qualities of 'original' documents (texts, images or models) and their reproductions
- Learn how to use archival documents in relation to current or historic sites
- Learn to interpret landscape architectural design in its historical (economic, cultural, societal, spatial) context
- Learn how to interpret landscape architectural design as part of an overall landscape intervention, where also other parties than the designer are involved (commissioners, administrators, executors, maintenance departments, users/inhabitants, funders etc.)

What will students learn?

- Conduct independent architectural historical research on a given theme.
- Get adequate historical and historiographical overviews of a topic.
- Carry out a historically layered, visual and spatial analysis of a building, site or (urban) landscape.
- Critically distinguish various (historical) approaches to architecture, city and landscape and relate them to current debates.
- Choose appropriate sources to answer the student's research question.
- Be aware of the personal perspective as an architectural historian .
- Present and exchange ideas about the theme of the seminar with fellow students.
- Make a clearly defined, substantiated, and feasible academic research proposal.

Learning activities and assessment

The seminar is set up in two parts. The first is an introductory, collective part with weekly meetings, where the lecturer explains the overall theme and research methods and gives examples of topics, using a variety of sources, among which archival materials. During the second half of the seminar students investigate a topic of their choosing, which they present to and discuss with their fellow students. The meetings are every two weeks. The assessment consists of an evaluation of weekly assignments, writing and pitch of a research proposal and the final paper.

Key advice for teachers

The lecturer can use archival materials in the introduction of the seminar topic. It is best to select a broad range of sources to inspire students and to indicate that designs or texts are just two of many options. Pre-selection and delimitation of materials is possible but should not be necessary at this level

On field trips, bring reproductions of archival materials (prints, drawings, plans, photos, descriptions, newspaper clippings) to compare a former situation with the actual one.

Let students autonomously choose a topic (within the collective theme of a seminar) and search sources in a controlled way. Leave some room for them to 'get lost' and make mistakes, without running the risk of not being able to get results.

Push students to start writing their paper in time and not endlessly continue the research – a common trap when you get enthusiastic about materials you find.

Stress the importance of interim self-reflection and peer review to assess the progress of the research process. As the seminar progresses, delegate tasks to students (organisation of field trips, way to approach the collective classes). The more they 'own' their course, the more you learn about what they need and the more autonomous they will learn to be.

Students in this master have different backgrounds, like architectural history, history, design. Historians usually need to improve their ability to analyse visual and spatial sources, students with a design background need to improve historical research methods and concepts; it has proven successful to let students learn from each other and benefit from the multi-disciplinarity in the classroom to understand that a topic can be approached from different angles.

Assignment

Part 1 (8 weeks)

1 Introduction and demonstration

The lecturer introduces the topic and the historical context and gives one or more examples of topics that fit the theme, showing archival materials. The lecturer demonstrates methods of research, stressing that students should look both to designs and the context in which they were built. What other parties were involved, did they influence the outcome?

2 Collective study and discussion

Collective study and discussion of basic information (literature – contemporary and historical text and images), based on mental maps by the students.

3 Explore

Students visit the site and explore plausible locations for archival material.

4 Proposal

Students present a topic of choice, a starting thesis, their approach and a preliminary list of sources (literature and archival materials)

Part 2 (8 weeks)

5 Individual research

Students start their individual research and writing trajectory.

6 Feedback

Students produce interim reports by students on the progress of their research. They discuss their findings and necessary adjustments together and with the teacher. Students peer review each other's research.

7 Practicum source criticism and analysis

Practicum on source criticism and analysis based on the sources used by the students: how to use literature and archival sources in your research (selection, analysis, interpretation).

8 Individual tutorials

Feedback of the lecturer on the results, tips and compliments.

9 Final product

Discussion and writing of individual final papers.

References

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Figure 21 left and 22 right: One of the students studied the role of participatory processes in the Dutch national programme for experimental housing district design in the 1970s. She found children's drawings as part of the participatory design process by an interdisciplinary planning team that contributed to the open space design of the district. Text in the black-and-white drawing: 'I would love to have forests. And then preferably a bit of mud. So you can make a nice mess. And ditches, so you can jump over them. And it would be nice to have cableways.' (Dutch National Archive)

Architecture, Cities, Landscapes: History and Heritage Master thesis

Architectural History, 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

The use and interpretation of archival documents in (landscape) architecture history is a basic skill. Students should be able to independently and deliberately decide whether archival research is needed to answer their self-formulated research question and how and where to locate the needed materials. As their choice of topic for the master thesis is free, not all students conduct archival research.

What will students learn?

- Conduct independent (landscape) architectural historical research by systematically and critically collecting, interpreting, and engaging with information from archival documents on a self-chosen topic in the field of landscape architecture.
- Identify and engage with overarching themes and interrelationships within the built and natural environment, drawing on a wide variety of primary and secondary sources, being able to understand how archival sources relate to other types of sources such as literature, site analysis.
- Autonomously draw up a research question or thesis and know what sources and methods are suitable to investigate it.
- Use information from archival documents to apply conceptual, analytical, and problem-solving skills in new or unfamiliar landscape contexts.
- Clearly and concisely present complex spatial, historical, and theoretical problems to both specialist and non-specialist audiences.
- Produce a well-structured academic thesis or equivalent research output (e.g. design-research portfolio) that demonstrates mastery of academic writing or presentation in the field.
- Demonstrate sufficient autonomy, self-direction, and reflective learning skills to pursue further academic or professional development.

Learning activities and assessment

Students are required to participate actively in the research seminar (see nr 15, p 47) and individually present concepts for their thesis and a clearly written and well-structured final paper at an academic level. They take part in a plenary research colloquium for the presentation of research progress and peer review, in addition to individual tutorials.

The use of archival materials is assessed quantitatively and qualitatively: is the selection of archival documents sufficient and correct, are the sources suitable to answer the research question? In the colloquium students are asked to comment each other's research questions and selection of sources, so they learn to reflect on the choices they make, not just based on their own experiences, but also that of others.

The image added shows the example of a student research into ecological urban landscape design in the Netherlands in the 1970s and 1980s. On one of the case studies, a recreational area near Amsterdam, there was a huge archive, containing a wealth of sketches, final designs and management plans, which enabled the student to analyse the design process. Because of the large quantity, it was hard to make an adequate selection, which called for support of the supervisor. Another problem was that, initially, the student only presented the outcome of the analysis of the archival documents, not the analytical process itself or the quality of the documents. Though it was not the research object, the archival documents were mainly seen as containing information to be used in current design practice, not to understand the historical design process itself (which was the actual object of research).

Figure 23: Recreational area Twiske, Amsterdam. Management plan, 1974-1975. Master Thesis H. Bloemers (2023) *Ontworpen spontaniteit. De benadering van ecologie in de praktijk van het Nederlandse landschapontwerp van stedelijke gebieden in de jaren '70 en '80*, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.

This case illustrates the different uses of archival documents that a student needs to understand: the distinction between history as an instrument (to be applied in design or heritage practice) and history as a goal (to find and understand new historical information or to interpret historical places and ideas from a new angle).

Key advice for teachers

Stimulate students to autonomously choose a topic, adjusted to the approach and qualities of the student: some need to be encouraged to do more and look broader, others have to restrict their subject and number of sources.

It may be useful to give some examples of your own research, showing the variety in archival sources and the problems that may arise. Point out the limits of knowledge that can be retrieved from (textual and visual) archival documents and that texts and images are produced with a reason, for a certain commissioner, with a specific goal and in a specific historical (spatial, cultural, political, economic) context.

Triumph and disappointment are part of archival research, which students tend to underestimate, timewise and because some tend to expect that everything can be found, particularly online. On the other hand, doing archival research can be very supportive for students to develop confidence that they can contribute something (new) to existing knowledge.

It is important to maintain a good balance between instruction and guidance. Let students experience the excitement and pit holes of archival research by themselves, while staying focused on the research aim and adhering to the time schedule.

Assignment

1 Thesis

The thesis is written as a fully independent research paper in accordance with the standard academic design. It should contain the following standard components:

- Introduction with problem definition / research question
- Explanation of the chosen method(s), including accountability for the selection of material
- Answer to the research question
- Notes, bibliography, source references
- Illustrations if relevant (including source references)
- Appendices if relevant, in case of archival research: a list of archives visited
- Before starting, students sign a thesis contract and present a plan of work, which needs to be approved by the supervisor and second reader.

References

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Theory and Methods of Landscape Design and Landscape Planning Exercise

Landscape architecture, 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

Considering that in this module the archive used is an audiovisual documentary record, its use constitutes a primary source for acquiring the theoretical content to be learned. Students can receive the content to be learned directly from its author, rather than second-hand through the teacher. This approach makes the process of constructing knowledge richer, more memorable, and more active than the simple transmission of information from teacher to student. Active learning fosters deeper understanding and longer-lasting retention of concepts, models, and theoretical approaches. In this context, the teacher's role is to facilitate knowledge acquisition by clarifying doubts and ensuring that students engage with and master the intended content. At the same time, active learning and critical thinking skills are being developed.

What will students learn?

- Develop an understanding of Ian McHarg's landscape approach, its ideological foundations, the concept of landscape suitability, and his planning process .

Learning activities and assessment

Students watch a selected excerpt from the public television documentary *Multiply and Subdue the Earth* (1969) narrated by Ian McHarg while simultaneously answering a set of multiple-choice questions available on Moodle. Each question refers to specific timestamps in the documentary. Students may pause, replay, and review any part of the video within the allotted time for completing the exercise. At the end, they submit their responses and review which answers were correct or incorrect, with the opportunity to review the archive and correct the ones they missed.

At the end of the task, the teacher leads a whole-class discussion to assess whether students have effectively understood the content. During this session, the teacher asks questions and comments on concrete examples prepared in advance. This gives the teacher the opportunity to address any gaps that may persist after the task. The exercise is not assessed by the teachers, it's a self-regulated task.

Key advice for teachers

The tasks required to prepare the activity include selecting the documentary/video, creating a multiple-choice questionnaire with automatic marking, and uploading both to a platform accessible to students (e.g. Moodle, Google Forms). This preparation takes about two hours, but once completed it can be reused in subsequent years with a minimal investment of time. Video archives such as documentaries or interviews are readily accessible on the internet (e.g. YouTube, websites of Cultural Associations or Foundations).

Assignment

1 Preparation (teacher) (preparation time: 2h, first time preparation of the task)

- Select an excerpt from the documentary *Multiply and Subdue the Earth* (1969) [minutes 45 to 54], available on YouTube, and make it available on Moodle. Note: You may make the full documentary available and indicate to students the viewing interval relevant to the activity.
- Prepare a multiple-choice questionnaire with 8 to 10 questions, targeted at specific minutes of the documentary/archive and key moments, such as concepts, methodologies and techniques.
- Make it available on Moodle.

2 Assignment (duration time: 40 min.)

- Brief viewing of the archive (video)
- Respond to the questionnaire by reviewing the documentary, in order to achieve an in-depth understanding of the archive and identify the correct answer.
- After each answer, check whether it is correct. If it is not, review the documentary again and make another attempt.

3 Class discussion (duration time: 20 min.)

- Teacher promote a class discussion to consolidate the knowledge acquired, beginning by posing one question.
- Encourage students to explain the concepts, methodological approaches and procedures presented in the archive, in their own words.

The historical and ideological context framing the method, as well as comparisons with other methods discussed in previous classes, may also be addressed.

- Invite other students to confirm and expand on their classmates' answers.
- The teacher should guide the discussion, ensuring that all the key aspects of McHarg's method are addressed and clearly explained.

References

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Figure 24: "Multiply and Subdue the Earth" a television documentary by Ian McHarg (1969) as an archive for teaching landscape theory (Source: Paula Gomes da Silva)

Themes and Concepts in Landscape Architecture Course

Landscape architecture & Architecture, 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

Archival sources—drawings, photographs, plans, historical texts, and original documents—serve as key material for reconstructing and interpreting precedent projects. Students use archives to understand the spatial logic and design intentions behind historical works, and to situate them within broader theoretical and cultural developments.

Archives also support the practice of informed speculation when documentation is incomplete, developing students' ability to interpret and reconstruct spatial qualities based on fragmentary historical evidence.

What will students learn?

- Develop historical literacy and awareness of design culture by understanding landscape architecture as a historically situated design practice.
- Understand how projects were conceived, communicated, and evolve by analyzing precedents and transformation over time.
- Develop analytical drawing, representation, and modelling skills by using visual tools as instruments of analysis and interpretation.
- Form personal, research-based positions and develop a critical and reflective stance within discipline.
- Prepare for research-by-design across scales and context, and link historical understanding to contemporary practice.

Learning activities and assessment

Students conduct a comprehensive precedent study of a historical landscape architecture project. It includes lectures on history and theory that provide chronological and conceptual frameworks for researching landscape architectural precedents. Reading workshops and team quizzes support active reading, discussion, and interpretation of historical and theoretical texts. A visit to the National Museum of Norway is included to connect historical knowledge to direct experience of built works, artefacts, and representations. Next, the students conduct research on precedent projects (individual or in small groups): analyzing project context, evolution, authorship, and reinterpretation. Group guidance takes place every two weeks to help articulate historical analysis. The assessment is based on a portfolio that is submitted and presented at the end of the semester. The portfolio typically includes:

- Plans and sections of the project, analytically redrawn by the students,
- A critical abstract analysing the project's history and design intentions,
- A timeline outlining the historical development of the project site,
- Physical models of the project, produced by the students,
- Scans and copies of archival material used as part of the research.

Key advice for teachers

Provide students with methods for archival research and spatial reconstruction and provide students with a list of possible case study precedents that can be realistically researched within the frame of the course.

Encourage “informed speculation” where documentation is missing—this builds both creativity and critical thinking.

Use drawing and modelling not only as representational tools but as research methods.

Integrate reading seminars early to ground students in theoretical frameworks.

Ensure regular guidance to help maintain manageable research scopes.

Limited time frame. The course duration (one semester) that limits the depth of archival research that can be achieved. Projects are therefore approached through focused and selective investigation rather than exhaustive historical reconstruction.

Diversity of case studies. The wide range of projects studied results in variation in available documentation and complexity, leading to uneven depth and comparability across case studies.

Access to primary sources can be limited for international precedent projects, where access to primary archival material can be limited due to geographic distance, language barriers, and institutional access restrictions. As a result, students often rely on secondary sources and partial documentation.

Interpretative bias and partiality. The combined effects of limited time, selective documentation, and constrained access to primary sources—together with the wide range of teaching and analytical tools employed (drawing, reading, and oral presentation)—increase the risk of interpretative bias in the analysis and reconstruction of projects. These biases are explicitly addressed through guidance, critical discussion, and methodological transparency, and are treated as an integral part of the learning process rather than as methodological shortcomings to be concealed.

Assignment

The precedent study is not organised as a strictly linear or stepped process, but follows a more open structure. It is partially structured through defined working methods—such as archival research, analytical redrawing, and midway presentations—and supported by individual guidance every two weeks. This allows guidance to be adjusted to each student and case study in response to ongoing findings.

1 Collection and reconstruction

The work typically begins with the collection of archival material, followed by the reconstruction of spatial qualities, the study of historical context, and the analysis of the designer's intentions. Throughout the semester, students develop drawings, models, diagrams, and written reflections that demonstrate how the project was conceived, how it relates to its historical moment, and how it may inform contemporary debates in landscape architecture.

2 Workshops and application of representational methods

Workshops take place on representation, writing and modelling. Introducing analytical drawing, diagramming, writing, and modelling as research tools. Students apply the representational methods to analyze spatial, material, and conceptual aspects of projects.

They test clarity, precision, and communicative quality of representations in oral presentations, and form personal, research-based positions.

3 Product and presentation

The assignment culminates in a portfolio submission and a final oral presentation. The presentations foster reflection through dialogue, feedback, and peer discussion. They encourage comparison, judgement, and positioning within landscape architectural discourse. The overall integration of theory, representation, and site-based learning trains students to work across scales and contexts using historical insight as a design resource.

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Figure 25: Illustration for the final review of the course, featuring images developed by the students as part of their precedent case study research. Credits: M. Hernández Quintanilla. Student work by: Aramian, Z.; Arcans, D.; Bekkevold, C.; Berre, I.; Bugnon, F.; De Loof, T.; Di Lucchio, F.; Floor, L.; Flan, N.; Grammatikkaki, M.; Granberg, A.-J.; Hermansen, C.; Holt, J.; Hughes, M.; Iversen, M.; Mendes, R.; Ottar, A.; Peppas, D.; Rødberg, K.; Schrödinger, D.; Sem, M.

Urbanisation in Western Balkan countries Theory and research course

Architecture and Urbanism 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

Although presented as a theoretical course on urbanisation, its primary focus is on creative research, with a methodological framework grounded in the concept of landscape.

The course examines the historical trajectories and contemporary urban conditions of places and landscapes across the Western Balkans, situating them within the broader theoretical discourse on urbanisation. Particular attention is given to the interplay between spatial and social processes, as well as to the cultural specificities that shape these environments. Students engage primarily with cities, towns, villages, and recent hybrid formations that are experientially accessible to them, subsequently positioning their inquiries within the wider Balkan context. In this way, urbanisation is translated from abstract theoretical formulations into the tangible realities of everyday life.

Student creative research draws extensively on archival materials, primarily maps, drawings, plans, and photographs. The course employs a landscape-oriented methodological lens—a holistic approach to space across multiple scales—derived chiefly from morphology and phenomenology in architecture and cultural geography. Within this framework, terrain configuration, open space, green structures, and vegetation are regarded as equally significant to urbanisation as the built environment, infrastructure, and modes of spatial exploitation. Through archival sources, students reconstruct landscape morphology across different historical periods, identify historic and contemporary spatial patterns at varying scales, and critically engage with key planning and design projects addressing spatial form and landscape.

What will students learn?

- Gain knowledge of key theories of urbanisation and their relation to urban form.
- Deepen their understanding of the historical transformation of landscapes in the Western Balkans, focusing on prevalent spatial patterns across scales.
- Recognise the importance of open spaces as structuring elements of urban form and landscape, and appreciate their social and ecological value for the future of rapidly growing cities.
- Strengthen research skills through both collaborative and individual work. This includes locating archival materials and using them ethically in research and presentation.
- Enhance their abilities in spatial analysis by employing archival materials in graphic analysis and creative narrative.

Learning activities and assessment

Research activities are conducted in teams of up to three students. Students start with historical desk research. They engage with key secondary sources, recommended by mentors, to investigate the social and cultural context, as well as urban planning and design. Findings are presented to peers to disseminate knowledge and foster collective understanding. Then, teams identify and select relevant archival sources and materials, followed by systematic content analysis discussed with teachers. Archival materials may include historical maps, historical plans, research reports, historical photographs, and architectural blueprints where appropriate. The archival research is followed by spatial analysis and graphic representation. Students undertake spatial investigations and produce original graphic outputs on urban form, both historical and contemporary. These visualisations often draw on archival imagery, either as creative reinterpretations or as novel perspectives.

Between research stages, joint discussions and reflective sessions are organised. During these exchanges,

teams compare findings—sometimes examining the same location across different historical periods, or focusing on distinct segments or issues within a broader urban landscape. In addition, mentors provide individual consultations with each team to offer tailored guidance.

Students submit a semester-long research project in the form of a narrative and graphic report. Once positively evaluated, they engage in a discussion with professors on key theories and concepts of urbanisation, offering critical reflections on their connection to the spatial context studied in their research.

Key advice for teachers

Encourage creative practice: Student research based on archival sources is a distinctive creative method. It nurtures intellectual curiosity, fosters patience, and helps students situate their work within the wider world of ideas. This approach should be regarded as an essential learning strategy across all areas of spatial design education.

Highlight historical and cultural context: Archival materials are particularly valuable in teaching because they anchor research in the history and authenticity of specific places, while also providing a lens through which to understand broader socio-cultural contexts.

Promote graphic exploration: Archival sources open opportunities for discovering new techniques of graphic representation. They can inspire imaginative practices and serve as a rich source of creativity for students.

Balance guidance with independence: While teachers may suggest useful types of materials and indicate where they can be found—sometimes even partially providing resources—it is equally important to leave space for students to uncover new materials themselves. This openness fosters independence, initiative, and creativity.

Assignment

The assignment evolves with each student generation but retains its core structure: investigating and interpreting urbanisation processes, namely the transformation of landscapes within their socio-cultural context. Research may focus on either the contemporary condition of the landscape or its transformation across historical periods. The site is observed holistically—considering built structures, open spaces, green systems, terrain, and human activities—across multiple spatial scales and in relation to socio-economic circumstances.

1 Preparing the Assignment

Professors select the location, scope, and historical period to be investigated. They prepare a preliminary list of key archival and secondary sources to support the research.

2 Contextual Analysis

Students read and analyse secondary sources (books, journals, online materials) and conduct fieldwork in teams. The aim is to provide a concise description and visual illustration of the contemporary context.

3 Historical Analysis

Students visit archives to identify and select relevant materials, followed by systematic content analysis discussed with teachers. Archival materials may

include historical maps, plans, research reports, photographs, and architectural blueprints. Students also read and analyse secondary sources on the history of the landscape. Sources are used to reconstruct, describe, and visually represent the principal phases in the transformation of urban form and their socio-cultural conditions.

4 Spatial Analysis

Students analyse the contemporary state of the urban form (or a specific historical period) using geodetic bases, fieldwork results, and historical research. The aim is to characterise, describe, and visually represent the urban form and its typical patterns at smaller scales. Students employ a combination of techniques, such as mapping, collaging, diagramming, and drawing.

In historical and spatial analysis, new visualisations often draw on archival imagery, either as creative reinterpretations or as novel perspectives. Students should clearly demonstrate how archival material is used—whether as a base layer, as authentic source material, as part of a collage, or as the foundation for an original drawing, among other possibilities.

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Figure 26: The Urban Form of Banja Luka at the Close of Ottoman Rule (Late 19th Century). This map segment presents the urban form with an emphasis on fundamental spatial-cultural patterns: mahala—neighbourhoods organised around mosques—and čaršija—marketplaces and craft districts. As its cartographic base, a scanned original map of the city from the late 19th century has been employed.

Architecture of the City and Landscape Design studio

Architecture and Urbanism, 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

The design studio Architecture of the City and Landscape uses archival materials as a core methodological instrument for understanding long-term spatial transformations, inherited landscape structures, and regulatory frameworks. Archives are treated as an active knowledge base that enables students to critically interpret the cultural, social, ecological, and spatial evolution of complex urban–landscape systems. For the academic year 2024/25, archival research focuses on the Olympic mountain landscapes of Bosnia and Herzegovina, analysing the transition from the 1984 Sarajevo Winter Olympics through war and post-socialist transformation to contemporary environmental and spatial challenges.

Archival materials are structured into spatial-planning documentation, architectural records, historical media sources, and institutional documents, allowing students to reconstruct development trajectories and critically assess the gap between utopian planning visions and later conditions of abandonment, degradation, and resilience.

What will students learn?

- Understand socio-economic, legal, and ecological frameworks shaping landscape and urban transformation through historical documentation.
- Analyse relationships between people, buildings, and landscape across time using archival evidence.
- Critically interpret inherited spatial patterns and regulatory systems.
- Translate archival knowledge into spatial programmes, design principles, and narrative representations.
- Integrate archival research with fieldwork and contemporary data in evidence-based design proposals.

Learning activities and assessment

Students actively engage with archival materials at different stages of the semester. Archival collections are placed in the introduction to establish baseline knowledge of territorial development, planning regulations, and inherited spatial structures. During the research-analytical phase, students systematically analyse archival materials to produce morphogenetic, cartographic, and photographic narratives. In the fieldwork phase, archival findings are confronted with on-site observations, enabling verification, reinterpretation, and critical reflection. In the design and project development phases, archival research is repositioned as a design input informing scenarios, programmes, and spatial strategies. Finally, archival materials are integrated into final visual and narrative outputs, supporting design arguments and interpretations.

Assessment is explicitly linked to archival research. The research-analytical work, utopia/dystopia models, and final project book are evaluated based on students' ability to interpret, translate, and critically apply archival materials in combination with fieldwork and contemporary references. Colloquiums and the final exam assess how clearly students articulate the role of archival sources in shaping design logic and decision-making.

Key advice for teachers

Teachers are advised to systematically curate and structure archival resources, clearly distinguishing them from literature, field data, and contemporary sources. Archival engagement should be introduced early, revisited throughout the semester, and explicitly referenced in analytical and design outputs. Teachers should guide students in identifying which conclusions derive from archival evidence and how historical knowledge informs contemporary spatial strategies, ensuring archives function as active design instruments rather than passive historical records.

Assignment

Throughout the course, the use of archival materials and complementary research sources is differentiated and assigned specific roles within the research–design process. Archival sources function as the reference for understanding historical development trajectories, regulatory frameworks, and inherited spatial structures, while fieldwork and contemporary data serve to verify, reinterpret, and critically expand archival findings.

1 Understanding Context / Research-Analytical phase

Work begins with the systematic analysis of archival spatial-planning documentation, historical maps, urban and architectural records, and institutional archives. These materials establish the baseline for morphogenetic, cartographic, and photographic narratives and support the identification of long-term values and potentials across cultural, ecological, social, ambient, and economic dimensions. Field observations are introduced in parallel to confront archival knowledge with present-day conditions.

2 Critical Review of Regeneration Strategies

Archival sources are used to historically and spatially contextualize existing projects, while contemporary design references, policy documents, and theoretical literature inform critical positions and alternative interpretations.

3 Landscape Map and Principles Catalogue

Sources are integrated in a structured manner: archival materials underpin spatial mapping, typological analysis, and value identification, whereas literature-based case studies and field research support comparative analysis and the development of project patterns.

4 Utopia/Dystopia Models and Detailed Project Development

Archival research is repositioned as an active design input, informing scenario-building, programmatic decisions, and spatial strategies, while speculative thinking, user analysis, and contemporary environmental data expand the design scope.

5 Project Book and Presentation

Design decisions are expected to be explicitly supported by archival research, fieldwork, and literature, ensuring transparency of sources and methodological coherence throughout the assignment.

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Figure 27 (top): Sarajevo Olympic Capital - A map of the many sites, venues and attractions of the 1984 Winter Olympic Games in Sarajevo. Source: <https://www.spomenikdatabase.org/post/the-architectural-legacy-of-sarajevo-s-84-winter-olympics>

Figure 28 (bottom): Timeline – A Chronological Survey of the History of Skiing on Mount Jahorina (Bosnia and Herzegovina), 1870–1987. A particularly significant section of this timeline is devoted to data concerning the preparation, organization, maintenance, and the broader benefits generated by the Winter Olympic Games (1984). The documentary foundation of the timeline rests on archival sources—photographic, cartographic, and published materials—drawn from the Museum of Winter Olympic Games as well as periodicals.

Regenerative design Design studio

Architecture and Urbanism, 1st year Masters

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Bosnia and Herzegovina

Why teaching with archival materials?

This master-level elective design course develops advanced knowledge, methods, and tools relevant to preparing students to engage with pressing urban regenerations challenges in a way that is innovative, responsible, and deeply contextual. The intention of using archives in the course is to make students aware of the existence and availability of the archive and archival materials. By engaging with archival materials, students learn to trace the historical layers of urban development, identify patterns of degradation, and recognise the cultural heritage embedded in urban landscapes. Archival documents serve as analytical tools that are used into workshops and research assignments, encouraging students to develop evidence-based proposals that respect cultural continuity while promoting ecological resilience and social inclusivity.

What will students learn?

- Explore the social and cultural context, as well as urban planning and design through secondary sources.
- Decide when to devise regeneration strategies and to make design decisions for master plans and detail regeneration projects.
- Critically assess urban environments, conduct applied research, and propose innovative strategies that balance heritage preservation with forward-looking sustainable solutions.

Learning activities and assessment

Students are introduced to the typology of degraded urban areas, learning how to classify and analyse different forms of urban decline and to apply appropriate regeneration methods. They investigate examples of urban renewal in different contexts, developing their own intervention scenarios. Through multidisciplinary discussions and research assignments, students examine how cultural identity, economic factors, and ecological parameters shape urban strategies.

The course includes field research and site analysis, classifying different types of degraded spaces and proposing methods for their transformation. In practical exercises, students use urban planning methods and digital tools for spatial analysis, simulation, and visualisation of possible solutions. Student teams identify and select pertinent archival sources and materials for applied archival research, followed by systematic content analysis. They present the results to peers to spread knowledge and foster collective understanding.

Assessment is based on:

- Project Work: the ability to apply regenerative design strategies, conduct site analysis, and produce innovative, context-sensitive solutions.
- Seminar Participation and Discussions: active engagement in seminar debates and critical reflection on case studies, emphasising the student's ability to articulate ideas and challenge methodologies.
- Field Research and Case Study Reports: the capacity for applied research and critical evaluation.
- Workshop Outputs: track progress in integrating ecological, cultural, and economic dimensions into design proposals.
- Final Presentation and Defence: defence of project work (of the methodological approach and design solutions).

Key advice for teachers

Use archives and case studies actively: Don't treat historical materials as background reading only. Encourage students to use them as design inputs, linking past urban transformations to contemporary challenges.

Assignment

Students work with historical maps, plans, photographs, and documentation to recognize the layered development of the city, identifying continuities and ruptures in urban processes as well as patterns of spatial degradation. Research Phases:

- Contextual Analysis – situating the landscape within broader environmental, social, and economic contexts
- Historical Analysis – tracing the evolution of landscape use, development, and transformation over time
- Spatial and Value Analysis – assessing spatial structures, ecological and cultural values, and potentials for future development
- Archival Emphasis in Analytical Framework: Landscape Study Model

1 XL Scope / Regional Landscape

- Collect regional maps, cadastral plans, and documents on major infrastructure projects.
- Compare different time periods to identify changes in settlement distribution and natural resource use.
- Map continuities (e.g., persistent communication routes) and ruptures (e.g., disappearance of villages, shifts in land use).
- Formulate conclusions about the region's potentials for future development.

2 L Scope / Metropolitan Landscape

- Analyze historical metropolitan master plans and aerial photographs.
- Identify phases of city expansion and changes in transport networks.
- Connect archival data with current conditions of infrastructure and green systems.
- Assess opportunities for regeneration within the metropolitan structure.

3 M Scope / Local Landscape

- Gather local settlement plans, old street and neighborhood photographs.
- Compare archival sources with the present state of the area.
- Identify contrasts (rural–urban, regulated–wild) and trace layered development of local networks and nodes.
- Mark degraded zones and define potentials for renewal based on historical patterns.

4 S -Scope / Project Landscape

- Collect site specific archives: property records, building permits, historical photographs.
- Reconstruct the evolution of the space and recognize its cultural identity.
- Integrate archival data into defining project goals and development dynamics.
- Design interventions that connect historical heritage with innovative regenerative practices.

Figure 29: An example of the use of archival documents (published in the monograph “Dokumenti opstanka”, Sabira Husedžinović, 2005) in the regeneration project of the oldest house in Banja Luka from 1580 (Šeranić House), in the Gornji Šeher settlement in Banja Luka. The graphic attachments on the right side are from the master's thesis of Milica Borić “The new old spirit of Šeher - regeneration of the historical urban landscape”, 2022.

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Landscape architecture in a globalized world Design-research studio, mapping

Landscape Architecture, 1st year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

Better understand and reflect the processes of Modernization of international examples of urban development. Introduce the relevance of a “history of ideas” embedded in a site. The topic of the course is reclamation development in response to riverbank typology in a colonial context. The long lots patterns is a riverbank typology applied from France to Louisiana. The Long Lot Survey Method is a land division system of French origin with long, narrow rectangular plots perpendicular to a river, road, or canal, ensuring multiple landowners equal access and distribution.

What will students learn?

- Understand the relevance of historic maps and urban planning proposals.
- Appreciate the deep history of a site in different phases of development on the backdrop of the swamp landscape.

Learning activities and assessment

- Reflecting on planning/urban design principles of urbanization/modernization.
- Analyzing and uncovering different layers of representation representing advancement of Colonialization of the territory; Laying down a grid over the territory in ignorance of its landscape features.

Assessment:

- Group discussion on revealing the learning
- By incorporation of understanding and comprehension in the further design process.
- Interpretation of layers relative to contemporary maps and site visits.

Key advice for teachers

The canon of emblematic precedents and projects in literature is well established e.g. The “Nolli Map” of Rome. Archives offer a key entry to expand the canon of the discipline with historical materials. In this sense it’s worthwhile searching for unpublished material to be unearthed from analog physical archives. In this example the Berlin State Library: discovering a four part/ five sqm map with rich details which was not recognized by the larger part of local historians and architects at the time (2012). It may be worth the effort to follow antiquated inconvenient protocols of scheduling appointments/next day reservation for the benefit of discovering unpublished material.

Assignment

Acknowledge the multiple layers of representation in the map

- Depicting the landscape in great detail and resolution. Rare example of not limiting the map to the urban core, but also portraying its setting of today's metropolitan area at full scale.
- 19th century urban development: Projection of a grid of subdivision of urbanization on the territory. Proposed blocks protruding past the coastline.
- Showing the idiosyncratic long lots perpendicular to the river. With main house on higher ground and plantation and slave quarters on the lower end.
- Representation of the landscape details: such as the bayou St. Johns sinus curve of tidal channel, connecting to Lake Pontchartrain.

References

- [Zimpel Map of New Orleans](#) 1832–34, by Charles F. Zimpel. One of the most accurate and meticulous maps of antebellum New Orleans is the work of an eccentric 19th-century cartographer.

Figure 30 left: Zimpel map, 1834 New Orleans German Surveyor. Berlin State Library / map archive.

Figure 31 right: A piece from the ParadoxCity exhibition, which accompanied the 2009 University of Virginia School of Architecture Woltz Symposium on Adaptive Infrastructure

Éditions Art Workshops

Landscape architecture, 2nd year Masters

Agnès Prévost

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France

Why teaching with archival materials?

Two workshops organised by the Arts Department provide support for these final projects, including the Éditions workshop. Students produce a collective publication bringing together two types of content: Materials (drawings, plans, photographs, interview transcripts, etc.) from individual research projects carried out as part of the students' Master's theses and archives held at the École Nationale Supérieure de Paysage. Students had to explore the archives of landscape agencies and sites in order to reconsider their materials and approaches through older works and methods. Dialogue with the school's archives was not planned before the workshop was proposed.

What will students learn?

- The aim of working with the archives was to enable students new to research to take a step back and Reflect on students' own era using the school's archives:
- Reflect on changes in landscape issues, aesthetics and working methods, changes in the techniques and iconographic media used by landscape designers
- Archive and document landscape design activities.

Learning activities and assessment

This is a workshop of 24h (4 days of 6 hours). Students search the archive database for project sites or documentary iconography that resonates with the students' master's research. They select a few (10 to 15 maximum) images and look for meaningful links between these archive images and the materials provided by the students for publication. They expand the initial materials if necessary.

They research into layout and graphic design to create the desired dialogue.

Most of the feedback is given during the various phases of the workshop and the rest at the end, in the form of comments accompanied by marks.

Key advice for teachers

Pre-select the archive material to be presented to students and help them get to grips with it through small group discussions. Do not choose too many archive images; focus on just a few.

Let the students work in double-page spreads; establish the meaning between the images on the left-hand and right-hand pages without using text. Try out several different combinations, print them out to check the meaning and scale of the reproduced materials.

Preserve the integrity of the archive but manipulate personal materials or create new ones to produce the desired meaning. Take the time to process the digital images.

Assignment

1 Students

Select text or image materials from their Master's research.

2 Archivists

Prepare a selection from the archive collection to present to the students.

3 Graphic designers

Prepare a book template.

4 Archivists

Present the selected collection to the students and explains how to navigate the database.

5 Graphic designers

Present editorial examples featuring archive images and the different narratives or treatments that emerge from them.

6 Students

Spend an afternoon, accompanied by the archivist, searching for images that are meaningful to them in the archive collection and discuss them together.

Having selected the archives, reflect on the content of the publication. They create new images to interact with the archives, assisted by the photographer, who comments on their work. Photography and image processing. They try out different layouts for the section once content has been finalised (approximately 8 double pages per group).

7 Graphic designers

Give feedback on the layouts in progress several times.

8 Students

Make final corrections (text and images), including feedback of supervisors.

Print and bound book, under the guidance of supervisors.

Figure 32: *Ça passe*, collective publication of the 2024-25 M2 ENSP-V-M promotion. 21x29cm, 144 pages, printing papers diverse, printed at ENSPV in March 2025. Under the guidance of Jauneau-Vallance graphic studio, the photographer Pierre Seiter and the visual artist and teacher Agnès Prévost. ©ENSP-V-M, 2025

Historical Green Space Restoration Design Studio

Landscape architecture, 2nd year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

While archives can be useful in many design studios, including those focused on non-historical open spaces, they form a core component of the Historical Green Space Restoration Design Studio. In this course, working with archival materials is both essential and unavoidable. Archival sources enable students to investigate the original design, trace the historical development, and understand the cultural significance of historical green spaces—especially gardens and parks. This research provides the foundation for creating well-informed and accurate restoration concepts and plans.

What will students learn?

- Identify, access, and navigate a range of archival databases and repositories—including publicly accessible collections of historical photographs, postcards, paintings, cartographic records, and written documents, as well as more specialised or restricted sources.
- Process, analyse, synthesise, interpret, and critically evaluate archival materials.
- Develop an informed restoration strategy, concept, plan, and design for historical green spaces, based on archival materials.

Learning activities and assessment

Students investigate the historical development of a selected historical green space—typically a garden or park—through archival research and analysis. They will document and map the site's current state and condition, and subsequently develop a comprehensive restoration design project for the chosen historical site.

Student performance in this course is evaluated through three main milestones:

- The quality and depth of their archival research and analysis of historical materials
- The accuracy and thoroughness of their field research, mapping, and documentation
- The coherence, feasibility, and overall quality of their restoration design concept or project.

Students submit their work and are required to present and defend their outcomes in an oral examination.

Key advice for teachers

Provide students with clear guidance in the early stages on where and how to locate relevant archival resources and how to work with them. Help them understand what to analyse, what questions to ask, and how to interpret the materials. Most importantly, support them in integrating this analytical and historical understanding into their subsequent design process, ensuring that archival research becomes a meaningful foundation for their restoration work.

Assignment

1 Site identification and selection

Students choose an object of historical green space: garden, park or other landscape element.

2 Archival research

Archival material collection, review, analysis, synthesis, interpretation and evaluation.

3 Processing graphical archival materials

Mainly historical maps and photographs, digitalisation, vectorisation, graphical analysis (superimpositions, layer maps, timelines, etc.).

4 Field work

Visiting, walking, mapping and documenting the selected site of historical greenery, including a dendrological survey or a detailed inventory of existing woody plants using standard arboricultural methods.

5 Develop a vision and concept

Based on the archival and field research, students are required to develop a restoration vision and concept, including a sustainable strategy for future use of the site.

6 Develop a restoration plan and design

Using acquired knowledge, skills and competences during their landscape architecture studies, students are required to develop and deliver a landscape architectural design of restoration.

7 Interpret and present the design

Students elaborate conceptual schemes, diagrams, layer maps, including references to archival materials and different presentation formats (posters, portfolios, presentations).

8 Present and defend the restoration plan

The exam consists of presenting, explaining and defending the implemented restoration design approach, based on archival materials, they have to provide evidence for a sensitive restoration.

References

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Figure 33: Digital vectorisation of the historical landscape garden of the Coburg noble family in Pohorelská Maša (Pohorella) in Central Slovakia, based on a high-quality colour digital scan of the original cadastral map from 1868 (Source of the map: Archive of the Geodetic and Cartographic Institute Bratislava, Author of the vectorisation and figure: Attila Tóth, 2025)

Master research thesis

Module introduction to research

Landscape architecture, 1st and 2nd year Master

Sonia Keravel & Bernadette Blanchon

Versailles School of Landscape Architecture
France

Why teaching with archival materials?

This teaching module aims to teach students how to use landscape architecture archives in their research. In particular, we teach students how to use archives to do a critical reading of a landscape architecture achievement.

What will students learn?

- Formulate a research question.
- Conduct relevant research methods: survey, archival research, case study research.
- Understand the long history of a project and its successive transformations over time.
- Develop a critical perspective on projects.

Learning activities and assessment

Students learn how to collect archives from the various stakeholders involved in a project: pre-project site surveys, graphic documents (including plans, cross-sections and photographs) of the project at its various stages, texts, etc. They interpret and analyze these documents and conduct interviews with those involved in the project to fully understand the meaning of the documents.

Apart from the final evaluation of the thesis, students will be assessed on methods of landscape architecture criticism and how to use archives.

Key advice for teachers

Students must be independent: they must know how to search for archives themselves and conduct interviews with the various project stakeholders on their own.

Students must have ample time for this work (approximately one semester).

It may be useful to present the exercise as a kind of “police investigation”, where students ask a question based on a project they are familiar with and which raises questions for them. It is therefore essential to have a question at the outset of the work.

Problems encountered may include, for example, being unable to meet with project Landscape architects or access archives.

Assignment

1st Semester

1 Formulate question

Students formulate a research question and read up on the subject. They need to find one or several case studies related to the question.

2nd semester

2 Collect and analyse data

Students collect archives from the various parties involved in the case studies. They conduct interviews with the various parties to understand the documents, and interpret the documents in light of the interviews.

3 Interpretation and documentation

They graphically translate their interpretation and write the thesis.

References

Denis Delbaere (2021) *Altérations paysagères. Pour une théorie critique de l'espace public*, Parenthèses.

Sonia Keravel (2026) *La metropole par les parcs. Enquêtes photographiques sur les projets pionniers du Grand Paris (1970-1990)*, MétisPresses.

Bernadette Blanchon (2026) The potential of scholarly reading of constructed landscapes. Or the difficult art of interpretation, *JoLA*, 2026 2 (anniversary issue), p. 66-71.

All articles in the Under the sky section of the *JoLA* journal.

Initiation à la recherche, exemples de mémoires encadrés, Versailles. ENSP.

Figure 34: Examples of master thesis covers. One led to an article in *JoLA*, 1-2022 by Suzanne Rey previously directed by Sonia Keravel for her master thesis. The cover images are part of the research results.

Designing Public Spaces Design studio

Landscape design, 2nd year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

The course, with particular emphasis on modernization or revitalization processes, considers these activities as a factor in building the city's identity and shaping its image through public spaces design. The areas selected for design are an integral part of the city's urban layout and should be considered within the context of the site and its surroundings, including relations to their history. The course focuses on the design of different types of urban public spaces that link the past and the present – a case study.

An important part of the pre-design stage is to collect data on the site history and analyze changes introduced in the following years, resulting in changes in its spatial order, functions, greenery development, etc. The collected data from different types of archival documents, such as cartographic and iconographic materials, as well as written information, is crucial for understanding the genius loci and site history, as well as a basis for design decisions related to restoration, maintenance, or changes introduced at present.

What will students learn?

- Learn about the role of archival materials in the contemporary design of places - understanding of a wider perspective of the site based on its history.
- Develop skills in historical analysis, including the appropriate selection of content for its specific aspect or theme. Develop skills in synthesizing, interpreting, and critically evaluating archival materials.
- Learn interdisciplinary research methods that link theory and practice.
- Learn to design public spaces in relation to spatial-functional, social, cultural, and environmental conditions through the use of various types of archival sources presenting a different scope of information and their implementation.

Learning activities and assessment

Document analysis exercises, research-based assignments using primary sources, and thematic selection of different types of documents to link the gaps. The learning process is supported by a demonstration of document analysis on a selected example and/or review of other projects in which the results of archives analysis have been implemented.

Formal assessment of the stage of analysis based on archival materials and implementation of its outcomes and defined guidelines in the final design - presentation.

Key advice for teachers

When selecting a site for project development, the teacher should review whether archival materials are available. The collection process of archival materials takes much time, and the searching should be conducted in smaller groups of students focusing on selected archive types, etc.

The diversity of archival sources may help fill the gaps in the process of historical analysis, thus encouraging students to delve deeper into the site.

It is essential to refer directly to the archival materials as a direct frame of reference in the design process, ensuring that students understand the connections between the past and the present as a basis for their design decisions.

Assignment

1 Preparation (teachers)

The teacher selects materials in collaboration with the archivists and checks their availability and relevance to the studied site.

2 Archival visit (students and teachers)

The teacher presents the archival materials to the students, explaining the relevant aspects and discussing them with the students. Common discussions include teachers' explanations and students' questions.

3 Apply in the design studio (students supported by teachers)

The part of the project development related to the use of archives to learn about the history of the place and its transformations includes the following stages:

- Assignment of a project to find and interpret archival materials to answer research questions related to the specifics of the site arrangement and functions that have been changing over the years.
- Search for primary sources by visits to archives, libraries, and the use of digital documentation available online, etc.; materials and data selection based on different types of archival sources (historical and contemporary descriptions, articles, maps, photographs, etc.). Collaboration with archivist(s).
- Document analysis based on different methods (thematic analysis, source comparison, text review, etc.) following a structured approach that prompts noticing important details and rules of the space arrangement and its elements, contextualization of documents, and inferring the meaning.
- Graphical presentation of analysis results and formulation of conclusions.
- Development of design principles that respect the site's historical values, their comparison, and linking with conservation guidelines.
- Implementation process – application of guidelines in the project, including site adaptation to the contemporary conditions.
- Project presentation and discussion.

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Figure 35: An example of the archival materials used to identify changes to Dąbrowski Square in Warsaw as a part of the pre-design stage. 1. Plan of Warsaw: 1873 (W. Kolberg), Biblioteka Narodowa w Warszawie, sygn. ZZK 39 673; 2. Plan of the city of Warsaw scale 1:2500 (1936-41), Narodowe Archiwum w Warszawie, section: 1004/IV, Collection I (Maps and plans of Warsaw), sygn. K I 1243; 3. North view. J.H. Dąbrowski Square (Photo author: Rutowska Grażyna, 1969), Narodowe Archiwum Cyfrowe (NAC), sygn. 3/40/0/14/10, negative No. 40-W-10-2; 4. Warsaw: Green Square, postcard No. 430, before 1915 (Wydawnictwo K. Wojutyńskiego), Biblioteka Narodowa w Warszawie, sygn. DŻS XII 8b/p.19/5.

Ecological Narratives

Design studio (Research by design & Design thesis)

Architecture, 2nd year Masters

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Why teaching with archival materials?

The Ecological Narratives Studio is a year-long, group-based design studio for second-year Master of Architecture students. It responds to architecture's historic complicity in the climate and biodiversity crises by adopting a landscape-led and historically grounded approach to design. The studio challenges students to think beyond the building as an isolated object and instead to engage with architecture as a part of complex territorial, ecological, social, and infrastructural systems.

The studio is structured around two linked units, namely a Research-by-Design thesis and a subsequent Thesis Design project. Historical research, archival material, and site-based analysis and mapping form the methodological foundation of both units. Students are asked to interrogate how historic infrastructures were planned, inhabited and contested. They then use these insights to generate speculative, forward-looking design propositions that address contemporary environmental challenges.

Each year the studio adopts a case-study approach that often centres on post-industrial or infrastructural landscapes of power. The studios are supported by archival materials held in the University of Liverpool Special Collections, the Museum of English Rural Life at the University of Reading, and other local collections.

Archives are central to the studio's pedagogy. Students engage with primary historical sources including plans, maps, photographs, models, corporate publications, and promotional materials. These archival artefacts enable students to understand how large-scale infrastructural projects were historically imagined, legitimised, and integrated into landscapes and communities. The use of archives positions design as a historically situated practice, encouraging students to treat history as an active design agent. By working with archival material, students learn to question dominant narratives of progress, technology, and development.

What will students learn?

- Engage with architecture as an interdisciplinary, territorial, and ecologically embedded practice
- Understand architecture and landscape as being historically situated
- Interpret archival sources as design evidence and analytical tools
- Critically examine energy landscapes and post-industrial sites
- Use historical research as a starting place for speculative design propositions
- Develop collaborative research and design skills
- Reflect on the ethical and political dimensions of environmental design
- Use archival research and other methods as a way of developing novel readings of the chosen site
- Develop a systems-based, landscape-led reading of the site and subsequent architectural design proposition.

Learning activities and assessment

The use of archives is used most extensively during the first unit, Research-by-Design. This unit begins with a broad introduction to the chosen site and its historical, environmental, and infrastructural contexts. Working in groups, students are tasked with undertaking wide-ranging preliminary research to establish a solid foundation for their projects. They are encouraged to read the site simultaneously through historical and contemporary lenses, attending to traces of past industrial use, current patterns of use and neglect, ecological processes, and emerging forms of informal reuse. This encounter with the landscape establishes the site as both a material reality and a historically produced construct.

The unit begins with an early three-strand approach comprising a site visit, an archival visit, and a lecture. Students first undertake site analysis to understand the spatial, material, and environmental conditions of the site. This is followed by a visit to a relevant archive, where an archivist introduces the collection, its historical scope, and its relevance to the studio theme, supporting students to identify and work with archival sources. A subsequent lecture by staff with landscape history research expertise situates the site within wider debates in landscape architecture, architecture, and twentieth-century design culture. Together, these three strands provide the conceptual and historical grounding for students to develop research-led spatial propositions. This work is further supported by additional thematic workshops, including sessions on mapping methodologies and anthropological approaches to site reading, which introduce alternative ways of understanding landscape through cartographies, social practices and material cultures. These workshops expand the students' interpretive toolkit and reinforce the studio's commitment to multi-scalar, multi-disciplinary modes of inquiry.

Students then go on to develop a series of creative maps, analytical diagrams and urban and architectural scale drawings as tools for converting historical and territorial research into spatial understanding. The unit concludes with a public exhibition in which each group presents its research-by-design outputs. In this way, the unit establishes a rigorous methodological bridge between archival research, landscape interpretation, and forward-looking architectural and ecological design.

The thesis design unit that follows, builds directly on the foundations established in the research-by-design phase. While archival research plays a less explicit role in this second unit, students are expected to carry forward the insights, evidence, and critical positions developed in the first unit. In this way, archives continue to operate as an intellectual foundation for design decision-making. The studio places particular emphasis on continuity between research and design. Students are asked to demonstrate how their proposals emerge from, and remain accountable to, the historical narratives, cartographies, and site readings developed in the first unit.

Through iterative design development, drawing, modelling, and critical review, students develop a thesis project that articulates a spatial proposition for post-industrial or infrastructural landscapes. The unit culminates in a final design submission where each group presents a thesis proposal. Together, the two units establish a pedagogical framework in which archival research, territorial thinking, and ecological design are understood as interdependent components of contemporary architectural education.

The programme is structured around a series of critical review presentations throughout the academic year. These reviews function as formative assessments, providing students with structured feedback on both their research by design development, site interpretation and design propositions.

At the conclusion of each unit, each group present in exhibition format and through the design of a portfolio website and associated social media platform. These outputs form a core component of the summative assessment. They receive a grade at the end of each unit. A final grade is awarded based on their performance across both units, ensuring that assessment reflects the cumulative development of their practice over the full academic year.

Key advice for teachers

Devise a studio brief around a site that has accessible historical and archival material. This approach works best when the chosen site is supported by some surviving documentary record, such as plans, photographs, reports, maps, or visual material. Selecting a site with identifiable archival holdings allows students to build historical readings of place, trace change over time, and reflect on how social, political, technological, and ecological agendas have shaped the landscape.

Work closely with archivists. Early collaboration with archivists helps in identifying appropriate material, planning archive visits, and preparing students to handle and interpret historical documents, drawings, photographs, and models.

Encourage temporal and territorial modes of drawing. It can help to encourage drawing practices that foreground time, process, systems, and landscape change. This includes layered mapping, chronological sections, speculative timelines, and multi-scalar territorial diagrams.

Support speculative thinking that draws on historical evidence. Students benefit from balancing speculative design with historical insights. This can be archival material as well as historic cartographic representation of ecological processes.

Assignment

1 Preparation

Students familiarise themselves with the site context using maps, plans, and any readily available historical material. The educator will provide guidance on key historical and ecological themes to explore.

2 Archive Visit

Students visit a relevant archive where an archivist introduces the collection and highlights notable documents, plans, and models. Students handle the material, take notes, and photograph elements where permitted.

3 Site Visit

Students visit the site to gather observational, photographic, and other measurable data. They compare the historical record with contemporary conditions, noting changes in landscape, infrastructure, and ecology.

4 Expert Lecture and Analysis

A lecture from a landscape historian situates the site in the broader history of landscape architecture. Students reflect on this context and integrate insights into their research.

5 Research-by-Design Development

Students translate archival and site-based research into creative outputs, including maps, diagrams, and architectural drawings. Time-based representations are encouraged, alongside multi-scalar landscape analyses.

6 Supplementary Workshops

Students participate in additional workshops (mapping, ethnography) to enrich site readings and test design hypotheses.

7 Presentation and Exhibition

Students produce a research-by-design proposal that synthesises archival research, site observations, and analytical drawings. This should result in a novel reading of their site with a clear design question for them to build on in the following unit. Work is presented in a public exhibition, online platforms, and reviewed in iterative critiques to demonstrate learning outcomes.

8 Assessment

The final grade is awarded based on evidence of critical engagement and a research-by-design proposition for their site that addresses the relevant themes.

9 Thesis Design Development

Building on the research-by-design outputs, student groups develop a multi-scalar, landscape-led architectural proposal for the site. They integrate historical insights, ecological analysis, and design strategies explored in the first unit, while developing a design intervention. Students are encouraged to explore architectural outputs that include novel forms of adaptive reuse, nature-based solutions, and multi-functional landscapes that respond to contemporary environmental and social challenges. The archival research informs material, spatial, and ecological strategies, even as the emphasis shifts toward forward-looking design.

10 Final Presentation and Assessment

Students present their thesis designs in a public exhibition and on digital platforms (website, social media).

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Figure 36: Reclaiming the River Studio Group's landscape and architectural design proposal for Fiddler's Ferry Power Station. Group Reclaiming the River 2024-2025. Instagram handle: reclaiming_the_river

Cultural Landscape and Traditional Architecture Seminar

Heritage studies, 1st year PhD

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Why teaching with archival materials?

This module focuses on the study of cultural landscapes and vernacular architecture through an interdisciplinary approach and is intended for students with diverse academic backgrounds within the scope of their doctoral studies. Archival research is understood as a fundamental methodology, to be integrated with other approaches, for interpreting the various cycles of construction and transformation of landscapes and architectures, aiming to contribute to the delimitation, identification, or definition of their heritage value.

What will students learn?

- The transversal skills to be developed throughout the course focus on interpreting the processes of transformation in traditional landscapes and architectures, privileging an inter-scalar understanding of cultural models of organizing spaces and activities.
- At the methodological level, students are expected to identify different possible disciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches, and to structure and develop a research project that aligns the chosen approach with the object of study.
- Among the different approaches considered, documentary research is particularly encouraged, with emphasis placed on three fundamental types of documentary sources:
 - Cartographic and iconographic documentation (with particular focus on historical cartography);
 - Official and administrative documentation (including institutional archives, tax registers, agricultural inventories, municipal regulations, and architectural surveys and projects);
 - Notarial documentation (including deeds, inventories, and emphyteutic or leasehold contracts).
- Documentary research, whether based on primary or secondary sources, is combined with other tools depending on the students' previous training. These may include fieldwork, the spatialization and interpretive drawing of written information, comparative cartography, and inter-scalar analysis, among others.

Learning activities and assessment

The learning activities unfold across three different levels. First, different study contexts are introduced, considering the transformation of landscape and vernacular architecture shaped by cultural models marked both by transitions between historical periods and by the long-term persistence of certain structural elements. These sessions also present the various methodological approaches considered and the role of documentary research in each case. They conclude with group discussions, in which students engage with questions raised throughout the sessions. The second activity concerns the structuring and development of the individual research project, supported by scheduled supervision and discussion sessions throughout the semester. The third activity focuses on communication skills, involving the preparation of the final presentation, which may take place in sessions open to external guests.

Assessment is based on participation in discussion sessions (including lectures, presentation, and debate of individual work) (30%), and on the quality of the individual research project (70%). Evaluation of the project considers the coherence between the structure of the work and the research object and objectives, the integration of different methodologies, and the extent to which documentary research contributes to the characterization of the object of study.

Key advice for teachers

The hermeneutic approach to historical documentation with a focus on landscape is, to a great extent, dependent on other disciplines (such as geography, landscape architecture, architecture, anthropology, and the natural sciences) that address aspects related to abiotic, biotic, and cultural systems, to the architectures and built elements of the landscape, and to community knowledge. Therefore, in each case, it may be essential to foresee, within the course plan, the articulation with other curricular units and to situate the activities to be developed within the integration of teaching and research, with the aim of fostering diverse and adaptable collaborative networks.

Assignment

This course combines the discussion of various themes and case studies presented by faculty members and invited speakers (theoretical component) with the preparation of an individual research project, accompanied by group-based critical reflection on the multi- or interdisciplinary approaches proposed by each student. In this sense, the preparation of the individual project may involve the following assignments.

1 Topic and scope

Definition of the research topic and scope, in alignment with the course syllabus and the doctoral thesis theme.

2 Methodology

Definition of a methodological approach centered on documentary research, fieldwork (survey of structures or ethnographic observation), or preferably a mixed approach.

Selection of archive(s) and identification of documentary sources to be consulted / Definition of the survey area and selection of objects for in situ documentation.

3 Archival research and/or fieldwork

Interpretation of the processes of transformation in the landscape and vernacular architecture, involving approaches such as synthesis of key topics; integration of bibliographic and documentary research; comparative cartographic analysis; and integration of documentary and bibliographic research with the characterization of surveyed objects.

4 Critical reflection

Critical reflection on the contribution of the work to defining the heritage significance of the study object, and on the possible delimitation of its scope in view of a classification process, considering both the broadened typological field of heritage and the importance of community involvement.

5 Final products

Writing, submission, oral presentation, and discussion of the final work.

This set of assignments is not expected to be applied in full to every student project. Rather, students should consider and justify their methodological and structural choices in relation to their study object, prior academic training, and doctoral thesis theme. This constitutes one of the assessment criteria, as the course is part of a doctoral program in which students are expected to develop autonomy in structuring a research project, in articulation with the Thesis Plan curricular unit.

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Defining a teaching unit with archival material Workshop

Landscape architecture and related fields, Teachers' training

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Why teaching with archival materials?

This workshop equips educators with the skills and confidence to integrate landscape architecture archives into their teaching. Although digitised and digital archival materials are increasingly accessible, many educators lack the time, methodological tools, or pedagogical frameworks needed to work effectively with them. Archives are also often perceived as belonging primarily to historical research rather than to design-oriented or cross-disciplinary teaching. This workshop aims to demonstrate how archival documents can support a wide range of teaching units, from creative design studios to critical historical or theoretical analysis, and to open discussions about social and environmental issues across landscape-related curricula. Because landscape projects unfold over long timescales and involve multidisciplinary negotiations, archival documents offer crucial insights into processes, intentions, and socio-environmental contexts often absent from finished designs.

Rather than focusing on a single predefined project, the workshop is designed to be adaptable to a wide range of archival case studies (e.g., historic public park, post-war housing estate, modernist landscape project, industrial heritage site), allowing facilitators to select materials relevant to their own contexts, collections, or institutional priorities.

What will teachers learn?

- Identify and interpret diverse archival sources (plans, sketches, photographs, correspondence, oral histories, and selected secondary materials) using visual, spatial, conceptual, and relational methods.
- Translate archival materials into coherent learning objectives, assignments, and outcomes for different educational levels.
- Reflect on the role of archives in shaping landscape narratives, identities, and pedagogical approaches.
- Produce a complete, ready-to-use teaching unit that they can implement or adapt within their own courses.

Learning activities and assessment

In the workshop, organised as a hands-on collaborative exercise, participants work with curated sets of archival materials (plans, sketches, notes, photographs, interviews, and selected secondary sources) selected to reveal both design processes and broader social context. After a brief introduction, participants form thematic groups and collaboratively analyse the materials. Using a structured template, each group develops a complete teaching unit suitable for History, Design Studio, Theory, or Research. The activity emphasises comparison, clustering, and cross-referencing of documents, and concludes with group presentations and a collective reflection.

During the workshop, facilitators selected materials from Cornelia Hahn Oberlander's Children's Creative Centre Playground for Expo '67, held at the Canadian Centre for Architecture (CCA). The workshop takes 90 – 120 minutes.

As a workshop, assessment is formative and based on active engagement, evaluated through the participant's contribution to group work, their ability to connect archival documents to pedagogical aims, and their clarity in articulating how archives can support learning. Feedback is provided orally by peers and facilitators during the final presentation and group discussion.

Key advice for teachers

Select archival materials that vary in media and scale, allowing multiple interpretive approaches. Provide a clear but flexible structure, enough guidance for those unfamiliar with archives, while allowing room for creativity. Visual collaboration tools (Miro, ConceptBoard, shared drives, or analogue boards and post-its) help participants annotate, cluster, and compare materials. Encourage educators to treat archives not only as historical evidence but as catalysts for curiosity, critical thinking, and design imagination.

Assignment

1 Introduction (10–15 min)

Introduce the potential of landscape architecture archives for teaching, showing a few illustrative examples when possible. Archival materials can reveal design intentions, decision-making processes, and socio-environmental contexts that are often absent from completed projects, and they support critical reflection, comparison, and creative reinterpretation across history-, theory-, and design-based teaching. The workshop task encourages participants to translate archival evidence into concrete pedagogical strategies through the comparison, clustering, and cross-referencing of documents.

Present the aim of the workshop and briefly explain the context of the archival material /collection used for the exercise.

2 Form thematic groups (5 min)

Participants join one of four groups – History, Design Studio, Theory, or Research – according to their interests and teaching backgrounds. Each group should have 3-5 participants.

- Online: assign each group to a dedicated breakout room.
- Face-to-face: provide each group with the same curated set of archival materials.

Figure 38: Screenshot of the results of “Group 02 – Design Studio” from the workshop held during the joint seminar “Teaching with Landscape Architecture Archives” on June 30, 2025. The board shows the group’s collaborative development of a teaching unit, including notes on the unit description, aims and learning objectives, assignment steps, and expected insights and outcomes.

3 Initial exploration (15 min)

Participants examine the archival documents freely, noting first impressions and identifying key elements such as context, content, material qualities, and potential pedagogical uses.

4 Designing the teaching unit (30–40 min)

Groups develop a complete teaching activity based on the archival materials. Working with a structured template, they define:

- Title of the exercise
- Course, class level, and time requirement
- Tools and materials needed
- Teaching unit description (max. 200 words)
- Aims and learning objectives (What are the goals of this exercise, and what should students learn?)
- Assignment and step-by-step tasks (What are students asked to do, and what are the steps they should follow?)
- Expected insights and outcomes (What are the expected insights, reflections, or learning outcomes?)

5 Presentation (5–7 min per group)

Groups present their teaching units to the workshop group, explaining how the archival materials shaped their teaching concepts and methodologies.

6 Collective reflection (10–15 min)

A facilitated discussion invites participants to reflect on the process, share surprises or challenges, and consider how the developed teaching units can adapt to different institutional or cultural contexts.

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Landscape Stories

Workshop / Project-based learning

Primary school

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Why teaching with archival materials?

Landscape Stories is a project-based learning workshop that engages primary school pupils with local landscapes through archival materials. The project built on research from the AHRC-funded Women of the Welfare Landscape project, which explored the work of women landscape architects such as Brenda Colvin, highlighting her professional networks and design philosophy.

The project fosters place-based learning, connecting children's everyday environments to history, design, and ecology. It demonstrates the role of landscape architects in shaping social and ecological spaces and introduces pupils to the use of archival materials as sources of evidence. Through this, students engage in critical observation, interpretation, and creative problem-solving while developing a sense of stewardship for their local landscapes.

Archives are central to the workshop, providing place-based historical evidence that enables students to connect with the design decisions, professional practices, and social values of past landscape architects. The use of archival material grounds learning in concrete historical examples, fostering critical thinking and visual literacy.

What will students learn?

- Develop an understanding of landscape architecture as a profession and its impact on local environments.
- Explore the contributions of landscape architects and inspire young people to consider professional roles in design and related fields.
- Interpret historical maps, plans, and photographs as sources of evidence, understanding the importance of archival material in everyday learning and critical thinking.
- Appreciate the role of design, collaboration, and social values in shaping landscapes .
- Foster critical observation, spatial reasoning, and creativity in proposing design interventions.
- Encourage environmental stewardship and place-based citizenship.

Learning activities and assessment

The learning activity is delivered as a full-day workshop for primary school students, structured into four interlinked components to provide a comprehensive and engaging experience.

- **Fact Finding** – Students are introduced to landscape architecture and the work of practitioners such as Brenda Colvin through archival materials, including plans, maps and photographs. Interactive discussions and quizzes help students identify designed landscapes and reflect on the role of design in everyday environments.
- **Learning Walks** – Students explore the local landscape with overlaid maps and archival plans, comparing historical and contemporary features. Through observation and discussion, they learn to interpret spatial information, understand design intent, and connect archival evidence to physical sites.
- **Proposition** – Using insights from the previous components, students work collaboratively to propose their own designs for a chosen landscape. Activities include creating 2D plans and 3D models, incorporating elements such as planting, seating, play, and ecological features, while considering the historical and environmental context.
- **Exhibition** – Students' work is presented as part of a public display, drawing on interactive elements inspired by the archival research. This outcome encourages students to communicate their ideas to a wider audience and reflect on the significance of archives in shaping understanding of local landscapes.

This four-part structure encourages active learning, critical thinking, and creativity, and demonstrates how archival materials can be used to connect historical knowledge with contemporary environmental and design education.

There is no formal assessment in this workshop although informal observation is achieved through recognising pupil engagement, participation in discussions, and completion of design tasks.

Key advice for teachers

Successful delivery of the workshop relies on thorough understanding of archival materials and its relevance to the local site. Educators should conduct detailed archival research in advance to identify a local landscape and connect it to the work of a historically significant landscape architect. This is essential to make the material relevant and engaging for students.

Quizzes and introductory talks should be designed flexibly to accommodate students' prior knowledge and engagement levels. Fieldwork activities require preparation including site visits and the creation of overlaid maps and tracing materials, with attention to safety and logistics.

Central to the workshop is fostering creativity and experimentation. Students should be encouraged to explore design in ways that are meaningful to them through drawing and modelling. Conventional map symbols can be shown as a reference, but students should be prompted to invent their own visual language to express their understanding of place. Educators should guide students in translating observation into creative outputs while supporting collaborative work and discussion.

The workshop is most effective when students move between archival materials, their own sensory experience and mental map of the site, and direct engagement with the represented landscape in plan and model form. This approach encourages curiosity, critical thinking, and imaginative problem-solving, allowing students to connect history, design, and place in an experiential and participatory way.

Assignment

1 Introduction

Educators introduce pupils to basic concepts of landscape architecture, they are introduced to a mini biography of a landscape architect, the importance of archives, and local geography.

2 Active learning and consolidation

Pupils examine archival materials, complete quizzes on landscape issues, and answer questions about the purpose and design of historical landscapes.

3 Learning walk

The pupils visit the landscape being studied. Each pupil, or small groups of pupils are given a map of the site with an overlay of the historical plans. As a group they identify changes, continuity, and take notes on observations about the design of landscapes. The educator asks them to spot different features in the landscape for consideration in their own designs.

4 Create a design intervention

Upon returning to the classroom, pupils work in groups to create a design intervention by producing a plan and 3D model that reflects historical understanding, site analysis, and creative ideas.

Models are made up of different crafting and junk materials. They are encouraged to work as creatively as they wish. Conversations happen at each table where the students are encouraged to share a rationale for their design decisions.

5 Reflection and discussion

The session is closed by educators facilitating a classroom wide reflection and discussion on how historical design informs contemporary practice and environmental stewardship.

6 Public exhibition

Pupils present their work in a public exhibition, integrating archival artefacts, photographs, and their creative models and plans.

Through this process pupils engage in observation, critical thinking, map reading, creativity, and collaborative problem-solving while developing historical literacy and an appreciation of landscape architecture as a socially and environmentally engaged profession. These are mapped against the Key Stage 2 curriculum.

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Figure 39: Primary school children working with archival drawings and plans to learn about the history and redesign their local landscapes. Photo copyright Joy Burgess, Luca Csepely-Knorr & Laura Sanderson 2023.

Colophon

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